

21GRD10 QuantiAGREMI

D2: Good Practice Guide on the developed emission monitoring techniques for the CO₂, NH₃ and CH₄ characterisation, considering atmospheric conditions and for enhanced spatial and temporal coverage as well as target applications

Organisation name of the lead participant for the deliverable: WBF-Agroscope

Due date of the deliverable: April 2024

Actual submission date of the deliverable: December 2025

Confidentiality Status: PU - Public, fully open (remember to deposit public deliverables in a trusted repository)

Deliverable Cover Sheet

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or EURAMET. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

The project has received funding from the European Partnership on Metrology, co-financed from the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme and by the Participating States.

European Partnership Co-funded by the European Union

**METROLOGY
PARTNERSHIP**

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1	Abstract.....	4
2	Target applications and requirements for measurement approaches.....	5
	2.1 Background.....	5
	2.2 Overview target applications and requirements.....	5
	2.2.1 Emission factor assessment for national inventories or environmental assessment	5
	2.2.2 Development of new mitigation strategies and assessment of the efficiency on site	5
	2.2.3 Monitoring emissions in farms.....	6
3	Methods to quantify emissions from livestock housings.....	9
	3.1 Direct measurements using anemometers.....	12
	3.2 CO ₂ balance method.....	13
	3.2.1 Uncertainty and Validation.....	13
	3.2.2 Measurement Conditions and Constraints.....	14
	3.3 External tracer-ratio method.....	15
	3.4 Tracer Dispersion Method and Inverse dispersion modelling.....	16
	3.4.1 Measurement Setup.....	16
	3.4.2 Measurement Conditions and Constraints.....	18
	3.4.3 Uncertainty and Validation.....	18
	3.4.4 Examples.....	18
	3.5 Simplified method.....	19
	3.5.1 Measurement Setup.....	20
	3.5.2 Results.....	21
	3.5.3 Conclusion.....	29
4	Decision matrix.....	30
5	Further measurement requirements.....	31
	5.1 Requirements for measurement devices and set-ups to quantify gas concentrations.....	31
	5.2 Collection of relevant accompanying parameters.....	31
	5.3 Data processing and statistical analysis.....	32
6	References.....	33
7	Annex 1 - Uncertainty assessment of animal heat and CO ₂ production (INRAE, LNE, Agroscope).....	36
	7.1 Fattening pig.....	36
	7.2 Concerning the uncertainty budgets, we can see the following:.....	39
	7.3 Dairy cows heat.....	40
	7.4 Broiler heat production.....	42
	7.5 References.....	46
8	Annex 2 - Uncertainty assessment on Carbon and Nitrogen mass balance deficits for different animal productions.....	47
	8.1 Fattening pigs (experimental pig house, Brittany agricultural chamber dataset)	47
	8.2 Figure 1: Carbon mass balance for batch 1.....	48
	8.3 Figure 2: Carbon mass balance for batch 2.....	48
	8.4 Figure 3: Nitrogen mass balance for batch 1.....	49
	8.5 Turkeys (commercial poultry house, INRAE dataset).....	50
	8.6 Figure 5: Carbon mass balance.....	51
	8.7 Figure 6: Nitrogen mass balance.....	52

8.8	Broilers (experimental poultry house, INRAE/ITAVI dataset)	53
8.9	Figure 7: Carbon mass balance for batch 1.	54
8.10	Figure 8: Carbon mass balance for batch 2.	54
9	Annex 3 – example of output of the simplified method (see 3.6) when comparing one farm to a population of farms by using the “signature” concept.....	57

1 Abstract

This report provides guidelines, descriptions and a decision matrix on which measuring approach and method to apply for specific target applications. The aim of this task 1.5 'Comparison of reference methods, simplified models and evaluation taking into account various boundary conditions' is to describe and compare the two state-of-the-art sophisticated approaches 'CO₂ balance' and 'external tracer ratio method' for determining NH₃ and GHG emissions from livestock housing based on the improvements of Task 1.3 and 1.4. In addition to the CO₂ balancing method and the external tracer-ratio method further common methods to quantify emissions from livestock housing like direct measurements using anemometers, inverse dispersion modelling, inverse tracer method and simplified methods are also included and evaluated. A brief overview is provided, along with more detailed descriptions, examples, pros and cons, and the conditions, areas and limits of application of these methods. The report also contains a number of examples of method comparisons and uncertainty calculations carried out as part of quantiAGREMI. In addition, this report addresses requirements for measurement devices and set-ups to quantify gas concentrations as well as the collection of relevant accompanying parameters. It also provides guidance on data processing and statistical analyses.

2 Target applications and requirements for measurement approaches

2.1 Background

Emission data from livestock housing for NH₃, CH₄ and other greenhouse gases are required by different target groups (e.g. legislation, authorities, consultancy, farmers, etc.) for different purposes, e.g. (i) emission factors (EF) for national and international emission inventories, (ii) development and quantification of mitigation measures, (iii) evaluation of new mitigation measures in commercial barns, (iv) monitoring of emissions from commercial farms, etc.

Depending on the question and the objective, different requirements are placed on the measurement in terms of accuracy, measurement uncertainty, representativeness, temporal and spatial resolution, number of repetitions per compartment/housing or repetitions on several farms, temporal distribution of the measurements over the year, etc. In addition, the system boundaries (individual animal, housing compartment, livestock building, whole farm) and the spatial, meteorological and topographical conditions at the site play a role in the selection of the measurement approach. For the air exchange rate approach, the ventilation of the housing and the system boundaries are crucial. In addition, the technical equipment of the measuring institute and its expertise, as well as costs and practicality, can be further criteria for the selection of the appropriate measurement approach.

2.2 Overview target applications and requirements

The most important target applications for emission measurements in livestock housing and their requirements are described in the following (quantiAGREMI activity A1.5.1).

2.2.1 Emission factor assessment for national inventories or environmental assessment

For emission inventories, emissions are calculated from **emission factors** (EF) multiplied by activity data related to a unit of time. An EF thus indicates an emission for a specific category or system (production system, housing system, animal category, etc.). For example, inventory reporting is modelled based on different Tier levels (Tier 1-3). The level of detail in terms of differentiation by tier subcategories, management, mitigation options, country-specific information, etc. increases from Tier 1 to Tier 3 (IPCC, 2019). Country-specific EF are usually derived by consensus within experts from many measurements. Emission data for the derivation of emission factors for a housing system require systematic measurements on several farms throughout the year ('multi-farm sampling approach') to account for both farm-related and seasonal effects and/or a production cycle (Ogink et al., 2013a; Schrade et al., 2012; VERA, 2018). When measurement over the whole rearing period is not possible, assumptions and models can be implemented for interpolation of measurements. This step will probably add uncertainty to the provided EF. Examples of the use of the multi-site sampling approach as a data base to derive EF for housing systems can be found for dairy cattle (e.g. Schrade et al., 2012), pigs (e.g. Wolf et al., 2023) and poultry (Burns et al., 2008). When providing an EF for a housing system for a specific country, other data such as regional temperature data and animal parameters may be considered in addition to emission values to account for country-specific variability (Schrade et al., 2012).

2.2.2 Development of new mitigation strategies and assessment of the efficiency on site

Usually, to develop and evaluate new mitigation measures a 'case-control approach' is used. In the 'case-control approach', the effect of non-system factors (e.g. temperature, ventilation rate, feeding, stage of growth, etc.) between the measure ('case') and the reference ('control') is minimised as well as possible. If two (or more) nearly identical housing compartments are available, measurements of the measure and the reference can be conducted simultaneously, thus strongly reducing the effects of the housing climate and external conditions. In a high number of studies, measure and reference are

alternated between the housing compartments ('cross-over design'). Examples include feeding strategies in dairy cows (e.g. Schrade et al., 2023) or urease inhibitors in fattening pigs (e.g. Schulte et al., 2024). In the case-control over time approach, the measure and reference are measured in one housing or housing compartment at different times. Measurements are carried out continuously over the entire rearing period or over short but frequent periods. Moreover, since the rearing conditions (and sometimes even the climatic conditions) are controlled, the evaluated performance is optimal. However, to certify the mitigation performance, the measurement results or the emission value (determined based on measurements and interpolations) should be accompanied by their uncertainty, both for the reference system and for the system equipped with the mitigation technique.

A field evaluation is also desirable. In this case 'multi farm approach' is recommended, a mitigation measure is systematically investigated on several farms and at different times/seasons of the year (VERA, 2018) - as in the determination of an EF - and the result is then compared to a reference value. This approach is very laborious due to the large number of measurements required and is therefore expensive. Field evaluation also makes it possible to identify, on site, the best practices that achieve the highest reduction rates, or to associate a given level of reduction with the specific practices and rearing conditions of a particular building.

2.2.3 Monitoring emissions in farms

Monitoring emissions from livestock buildings in response to national or European regulations can be carried out using modelling tools, such as GERP (<https://monaiot.developpement-durable.gouv.fr/page/guides-sectoriels-gerep>), ECOGAN (<https://akisplataforma.es/en/news/ecogan-computer-system-information-transfer-shows-106-reduction-ammonia-emissions>). However, it is strongly recommended to verify the emission levels obtained with such modelling tools. To this end, it is advisable to implement "simplified measurement methods" based on simple on-farm measurements and a reduced number of measurement days (low cost), so as to cover a wide range of rearing situations (such as variations in climatic conditions within a building or between different buildings) (<https://ccc farming.eu/results/wp-outputs-deliveries/files/wp1/FinalReport.pdf>). An advantage of such methods is that results could be available near real-time and (initial) data processing therefore automated as far as possible. As this kind of methods allow the screening of a high number of situations, it can be also useful to detect "hot spots" or "good practices". This type of method can also be used to verify that emissions from the farm at a given time correspond to the EF assigned to the same category of farms.

Thus, with sensor technology fast evolving, important improvements regarding for example detection limits, accuracy, interferences, drift, longevity and prices have been achieved. This increasingly opens the possibility to continuously monitor emissions as far as other required information for calculations can be also be collected continuously.

Table 1 shows the currently relevant target applications for emission measurements in livestock housing with challenges as well as requirements for the methodological approach and the accuracy of the results.

Table 1: Overview of relevant target applications for emission measurements from livestock housing.

Number (used in D4)	Objective / Target	Challenges	Method requirements	Accuracy of results
TA1	EF for emission inventories and environmental assessment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Define system categories (livestock housing) for different animal categories • Multi farm approach: Conduct enough measurements to determine the variability within a category (representativeness of the housings measured) • Measure variability over a production cycle and over a year • Collection of relevant information regarding the system (feed, animal, climate, management...) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Low cost (does not require a lot of investments) • Easy to implement (does not require high skills) • Easy to implement in different situations: Measurements at different sites ('multi-site sampling approach') • Number of measurements per site adapted to the production cycle and the variability of influencing factors of the housing • Access to zootechnical data at the time of measurements 	Lower accuracy: but no systematic biases, or low accuracy can be accepted by providing a large number of measurements (different housings, feed, management, seasons, etc.)
TA2	To develop or evaluate new mitigation techniques	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Comparison with a control system ('case-control approach') • Could be two (or more) compartments within the same housing • For growing animals: If the technique developed is not based on a feeding strategy, emissions over the rearing period on a per-animal basis should be assessed. • Implementation of measurements over long periods and/or representative of production cycles (or taking into account changes in practices, physiology or climate in production cycles) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implementation of identical measurement technique in the control and test compartments • Sensors should be compared before and after measurements • Uncertainty on final emission results has to be calculated 	High accuracy required to detect low mitigation levels

Number (used in D4)	Objective / Target	Challenges	Method requirements	Accuracy of results
TA3	Test the efficiency of mitigation techniques or housing systems in practical farms	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Multi farm approach to test the efficiency with various rearing conditions (in function of the mitigation techniques principles) and climate conditions • Measure variability of emissions over a production cycle and/or over a year • Conduct enough measurements to determine the variability of the mitigation potential of the technique • Availability of a reference emission value (without mitigation technique) for the tested farm 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of measurements adapted to the production cycle and the variability of influencing factors in the building 	High accuracy required to detect low mitigation levels
TA4	Monitoring on farm emissions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High diversity of livestock houses, animal and manure management • Flexible method that could be used by non-expert people at acceptable costs and reflect the temporal variability in emissions • Availability of a reference value for comparison with the measured emissions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Low cost • Easy to implement and across all rearing situations 	The level of accuracy must be sufficient to identify best practices by comparison with a reference emission factor

3 Methods to quantify emissions from livestock housings

The aim of this chapter is to describe relevant measurement methods for livestock buildings with a view to their application, and to highlight the main advantages and disadvantages as well as the limitations and requirements. Measurement methods are presented for both mechanically ventilated and naturally ventilated buildings. Emphasis is placed on practical scale measurements with a view to transferability to practice, considering possible influences of real housing conditions (e.g. animals, housing climate, management, etc.). Methods such as chamber measurements for partial areas (e.g. from floors, lying area) are therefore not the subject of this report.

There are two types of approaches to quantify emissions from livestock buildings, whether mechanically or naturally ventilated: the direct approach, which consists of estimating emissions based on airflow rate measurements and gas concentration gradients, and the indirect approach, which consists of measuring emissions at a distance from the source. For the first approach, the airflow rate can be measured directly using sensors or estimated using external or internal tracer gases. These different methods associated with these approaches are detailed in the following paragraphs and table 2 provides an overview.

In general, for all methods shown in the following a representative sampling strategy is required both locally and temporally.

Table 2: Overview of common measuring approaches for livestock housing (modified from Hassouna et al., 2023)

Approach	Area of application, principle, description	Evaluation (pros, cons, important aspects)
Direct measurement of the airflow rate using anemometers	Housing (building) Calculation of the air exchange rate from velocity measurements and duct diameter	+ Direct determination of air exchange rate feasible – Only applicable for forced ventilated housings. Requires measurement on each fan for accurate estimation of the ventilation rate at each time step

<p>CO₂-balancing method (internal tracer method)</p>	<p>Housing (building) Calculation of the air exchange rate based on the concentration gradient of CO₂ inside versus outside the housing and its theoretical output by the animals and manure considering climatic conditions. Parallel measurements of target gases and CO₂</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Quickly applicable + Cost depends on continuous/intermittent measurement and number of air sampling locations - In cases of very high air exchange rates (e.g. high wind speeds or large openings) or very low wind velocities the gradient between inside and outside air might not be sufficient or inaccurate - All relevant CO₂ sources and sinks in the housing have to be included in the model - High inaccuracy under certain wind and/or housing situations - Manure CO₂ production has to be measured or estimated ⇒ Suitable for housings without an outdoor exercise area and with a sufficient CO₂ gradient between inside and outside; accurate measurement for housings without deep litter
---	---	---

<p>External tracer ratio method</p> <p>Tracer decay or constant dosing</p>	<p>Housing with/without outdoor exercise area</p> <p>Emission source is mimicked by the means of a dosed tracer gas; calculation of the emission based on</p> <p>i) Tracer decay: decrease of the tracer gas concentration, or</p> <p>ii) Constant dosing: the mass flow of the dosed tracer gas and the concentration ratio of tracer gas to target substance</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Practical conditions + Real-time measurements + Established for natural ventilation, tracer dosing can be adapted based on ventilation rate - High costs and high workload ⇒ Suitable for naturally ventilated housing systems with outdoor exercise area
<p>Inverse dispersion modelling and Tracer Dispersion method</p>	<p>Total farm including housing, outdoor exercise area, slurry and manure storages etc.</p> <p>Measurement of concentration of the target gas upwind / downwind of the source and turbulence characteristics; emission determination based on concentration measurements and a dispersion model</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Farm scale + Cost-effective, flexible - Not suitable for complex topography/surrounding area and low wind speed - No distinction between individual sources within farm or livestock building: e.g. housing, outdoor exercise area, manure/slurry storage, feed storage etc. possible ⇒ Suitable for whole farm assessments or farm buildings separated from other sources, if requirements concerning weather conditions and topography are fulfilled

Simplified method	<p>Naturally or mechanically ventilated building</p> <p>Average samples of air are collected using sampling bags inside and outside the building</p> <p>Concentration measurements in the bags are done either on sites or in laboratory conditions</p> <p>A questionnaire is filled with the farmer to be able to estimate the carbon inputs and outputs in the studied building</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> + Quickly applicable, flexible + Cost-effective - Accuracy depends on data available from the questionnaire and CO₂ gradient between inside and outside
-------------------	---	--

3.1 Direct measurements using anemometers

Forced (also referred to as mechanically) ventilated animal housings usually have well defined air inlet and outlet openings. Inlets are kept relatively small to ensure under pressure can be maintained in the building even when ventilation rate is low, and to minimize environmental influences (e.g. from wind). Air inlets / outlet openings can be distributed over (compartments of) the barn through the ceiling or flooring to reduce indoor air velocity and provide fresh air equally. Fans placed in the animal compartments and/or at centralized outlet points discharge the used air into the environment.

Despite the general concept being simple, many variations occur in practice. In compartmented buildings (i.e. pigs) every compartment may have its' own air outlet where emissions take place. To arrive at the total for the barn as a whole, many measurements are necessary, or assumptions need to be made. Other cases will see the compartment fans discharging into a large collection duct often leading to an end-of-pipe technique (air scrubber/biofilter). Non-compartmented buildings can have several fans in the roof, distributed over the length of the barn or grouped together. Depending on ventilation requirement at the time, not all of these may actually be in use. Finally in broiler houses fans are likely placed in the end facade, again in groups or even varying in sizes and running time.

With advancements in ventilation technology, increasingly fans are being monitored remotely also opening possibilities to log their performance. Not every method is as reliable, for instance logging of steering current compared to actual revolutions. Also, availability of (device specific) calibrations, maintenance level and age will determine accuracy. Especially soiling of the fan can cause fairly large deviations over time. Use of measurement fans can overcome some of these issues but also have their attention points. They should always be placed upstream (i.e. in front of) the working fan, at a large enough distance to maintain a laminar flow or by installing partitions to break up turbulent air streams. Even then the additional pressure drops created by the measurement fan may be influencing the performance of the working fan compared to those without.

For naturally ventilated buildings direct ventilation rate measurements are not feasible. Recent research (Coorevits et al., 2025), however, operationalised an indirect method using wind speed measurements. Still requiring fairly optimal conditions like doors being closed, this approach is more useful for research but does not offer sufficient accuracy for monitoring purposes.

3.2 CO₂ balance method

This method is based on the hypothesis that ventilation determines the relationship between the production of CO₂ in the building and the difference in CO₂ concentrations between the inside and the outside of the building. The total production of CO₂ in the building can be estimated from the number and type of animals, the presence of litter and the production of CO₂ by the heating if appropriate. The airflow of the ventilation system Q_{CO_2} (m³ h⁻¹) can be expressed using the following equation

$$Q_{CO_2} = \frac{(CO_{2_{animals}} + CO_{2_{Manure}} + CO_{2_{Heating}})}{C_{Ind} - \frac{C_{out} \times \rho_{Ind}}{\rho_{out}}} \times 10^{-6}$$

where $CO_{2_{animals}}$ (m³ CO₂ h⁻¹) is the CO₂ produced by the animals and $CO_{2_{manure}}$ and $CO_{2_{heating}}$ by the manure and the heating system when gas (or fuel) is used inside the house,

C_{ind} and C_{out} (ppmv) are the CO₂ concentrations inside and outside the building, and ρ_{ind} and ρ_{out} (kg dry air.m⁻³ moist air) are the densities of the inside and outside air.

$CO_{2_{animals}}$ is estimated from the heat produced by the animals (W) using the following equation:

$$CO_{2_{animals}} = CO_{2_{hpu}} \times H_{animals}$$

where $CO_{2_{hpu}}$ is the production of CO₂ for 1000 W heat produced in the building (m³ CO₂ h⁻¹) and $H_{animals}$ is the total animal heat production in the house which can be calculated using the values from the literature (Pedersen et al., 2008; DIN 18910).

$CO_{2_{heating}}$ is calculated from the fuel consumption and the associated emission factors.

$CO_{2_{manure}}$ is ignored in some models when the manure is liquid. Other models take into account the storage of slurry in the barn by using a correction factor. For barns with solid manure, it depends on the quantity and biological activity of the manure: (i) when litter input per animal is small and floor is cleaned on daily schedule, $CO_{2_{manure}}$ is small; (ii) when litter input per animal-place increase and duration of accumulation increases (e.g. deep-litter systems, top-dressing systems), $CO_{2_{manure}}$ must be estimated to avoid significant bias in emission estimate.

3.2.1 Uncertainty and Validation

Nevertheless, when analysing this equation, it is clear that the accuracy of this method depends strongly on estimating CO₂ production by the animals and measuring CO₂ concentrations accurately. CO₂ production varies by animal breed, weight, activity, productivity, and pregnancy, but not all of these factors can be considered in the calculations as the models are not specifically calibrated to all this information. In dairy barns with milking robot and outdoor grazing area, animal number and animal distribution in the barn vary with time, inducing specific adaptations of measurement strategies to deliver representative "annual emission factor". Moreover, some farmers use different animals (e.g. dairy cows, dry cows, calves, etc.) and different manure management strategies (e.g. liquid and solid manure; floor cleaning frequencies) in the same barn. This can induce spatial variability in inside gas concentrations and proportion with CO₂ as well as differences between different periods. Uncertainties calculations have been made in the framework of quantiAGREMI A1.5.3 with existing datasets (see annex 1). Knowledge of precision will increase from improving models linking influencing factors (climate, animal and manure

management, etc.) and emissions and from improving knowledge of these factors on the farm scale. This last issue depends on farmer's motivation to be involved in emission management and share information (Luostarinen et al., 2017). Knowledge of trueness will increase from improving duration of survey as cumulating emissions over an increasing observation period will integrate a higher variability of conditions, hazards and associated management responses for the same farm management system.

One way to ensure that the emissions measurements taken are realistic is to compare of the cumulative measured emissions mass balance deficits over the measurement period if the uncertainty associated to the calculated mass balance deficit is acceptable. This should be done whatever the implemented measurement method.

Mass balance approach estimates emissions based on changes in stocks over time, without the need to measure emissions directly. This method considers that the mass balance deficit (difference between inputs and outputs) for each element (N, C or H₂O) is the total emissions rather than emissions of specific gases (e.g. NH₃, N₂O, CH₄, CO₂). It does not require using specific sensors but depends on the technical and livestock management data available, characterization of the manure and feed (figure 1). To test the validity of the data used to calculate the mass balances, those of non-volatile elements such as phosphorus (P) and potassium (K) must be calculated. As the latter elements are non-volatile, their mass balance deficits should be zero, but the data used in calculations will have uncertainty, especially under commercial conditions. If the mass balance deficit for P and K is too high (e.g., > 15%), then the estimates of total N and C emissions with this approach must be reconsidered.

Figure 1. Mass balance approach applied to an animal house to evaluate global N, C and water gas emissions

Uncertainty associated with the N, C mass balances have been calculated in the framework of quantiAGREMI A1.5.4 for different existing data sets for pigs, poultry and cattle (annex 2).

3.2.2 Measurement Conditions and Constraints

When measuring CO₂ concentrations, attention should be paid to the concentration difference between inside and outside. Open houses, such as those for dairy cattle, tend to have a small CO₂ concentration difference. For this type of house, the precision and resolution of the device used to measure CO₂ should be high. In houses with deep litter, manure can produce almost as much CO₂ as the animals (Jeppsson, 2000). This additional contribution to CO₂ emissions must thus be considered when calculating the ventilation rate. Nevertheless, it can vary depending on how the deep litter is managed, the climate, and animal excretion, but knowledge about deep-litter processes and emissions is scarce, which makes it difficult to estimate ventilation rate accurately for houses which contain it. For houses without deep litter, Ogink et al. (2013) indicated that manure can be ignored in calculations as it contributes less than 5% of total CO₂ production.

3.3 External tracer-ratio method

In contrast to internal tracer methods, such as the CO₂ balancing method, the external tracer-ratio method uses artificial tracer gases. The external tracer ratio method is therefore more robust to very high wind speeds and can be used in housing systems with very large air exchange openings (e.g. Edouard et al., 2016; Mohn et al., 2018; Ogink et al., 2013b; Schiefler, 2013) as well as in housing systems with outdoor exercise areas for dairy cattle (Schrade et al., 2012) and fattening pigs (Berry et al., 2005; Wolf et al., 2023).

The principle of the external tracer-ratio method is based on the assumption that the tracer gas behaves in the same way as the target gas and thus reflects the emission source(s). Therefore, it is important to have a good representation of the emission source by the release of the tracer gas as well as a good mixing of tracer and target gas, which allows a comparable transfer of tracer and target gas from the emission source to the sampling points/lines (figure 2).

Figure 2. Schematic example of the tracer-ratio method in a naturally ventilated housing with injection of the tracer gas close to the emitting sources of the target gas and sampling lines for both the tracer gas and the target gas in well mixed air.

The emission or mass flow of the target gas (\dot{m}_{target}), is calculated from the ratio of the background corrected concentrations of the target gas (C_{target}) and the tracer gas (C_{tracer}) and the known mass flow of the tracer gas (\dot{m}_{tracer}), as given in equation below:

$$\dot{m}_{\text{target}} = \frac{\dot{m}_{\text{tracer}} \times C_{\text{target}}}{C_{\text{tracer}}}$$

According to Phillips et al. (2001) a suitable artificial tracer gas should be safe, chemically inert, perfectly mix with ambient air, easily measurable, not available at high concentrations in ambient and/or background air, and inexpensive. The most common tracer gas used in livestock housings is sulphur hexafluoride (SF₆) (e.g. Snell et al., 2003; Berry et al., 2005; Van Duinkerken et al., 2011; Edouard et al., 2016; Wolf et al., 2023). In Swiss studies a dual tracer ratio method using a second tracer gas trifluoromethyl sulphur pentafluoride (SF₅CF₃) was applied to quantify emissions from housing systems with a separated outdoor exercise area (Schrade et al., 2012) or from different compartments (Mohn et al., 2018; Poteko et al., 2020; Schrade et al., 2023). Due to the greenhouse effect and the limited availability of SF₆ and SF₅CF₃, alternative tracer gases are being searched for. Within the quantiAGREMI project (see A1.3.6) ethane (C₂H₆) and ethine (C₂H₂) have been selected, evaluated in lab experiments and proven to be the most suitable replacements for established tracer gases (see also report D1 and

project report A1.1.8). For emission measurements in a German pig housing CF_4 (carbon tetrafluoride) is used beside SF_6 as second tracer gas (source University of Kiel/LUFA). However, the greenhouse effect of CF_4 is not much lower than that of SF_6 / SF_5CF_3 .

The uncertainty of the emission mass flow was estimated using the law of error propagation. Assuming uncorrelated input quantities the total uncertainty was calculated as the square root of the sum of error squares, i.e. partial derivatives multiplied with individual uncertainty contributions. In short, the following relative uncertainties were considered: concentration of the dosed tracer gas ($\pm 2\%$, manufacturers specifications), flow of the dosed tracer gas ($\pm 3\%$, manufacturers specifications), concentration of the analysed target species ($\pm 1\%$ for CO_2 and CH_4 , 5% for NH_3), concentration of the analysed tracer gas ($\pm 3\%$ for SF_6 and SF_5CF_3). In addition, an experimentally determined uncertainty contribution, which reflects the limited representativeness of tracer dosing for areal and point emission sources and limited homogeneity of tracer / target gas mixing was considered (Mohn et al., 2018). For areal and point emission sources the relative uncertainty for 10 minute / daily averages was assumed to be $12 / 5\%$ and $24 / 7\%$. This clearly indicates that for the studied setting uncertainties are dominated by representativeness and homogeneity of mixing and not the applied tracer dosing and analytics. For typical applications in naturally ventilated housing (enhancement in target gases: 100 ppm CO_2 , 10 ppm CH_4 , 2 ppm NH_3 and tracer gases: $100 \text{ ppb of SF}_6 / \text{SF}_5\text{CF}_3$) total uncertainties were in the range $13 - 14 / 7 - 8\%$ and $25 / 9 - 10\%$ for areal and point emission sources for 10 min / daily averages. Three tracer gas release techniques can be differentiated: (i) constant injection method, (ii) concentration decay method and (iii) constant concentration method (Ogink et al., 2013). Of those, only the concentration decay method (e.g. Schiefler, 2013; Snell et al., 2003) and the constant injection method (e.g. Edouard et al., 2016; Mohn et al., 2018; Schrade et al., 2012, 2023; Van Duinkerken et al., 2011; Wolf et al., 2023) are used in livestock housings. For the constant injection method, a known mass flow of the tracer gas is dosed, which mimics the dynamic flow and the dilution of the target gas(es). The concentration decay method is used to calculate the ventilation rate by injecting a defined amount of tracer gas at specified intervals and recording the decrease in tracer gas concentration over a specified period of time.

In terms of robustness and areas of application, the external tracer-ratio method is more robust and accurate than balancing methods using internal tracers. However, the purchase and injection of tracer gas as well as their analysis are associated with a higher workload and higher costs.

A comparison of the external tracer ratio method and the CO_2 balancing method based on data of measurements in three seasons and two compartments of the experimental dairy housing for emission measurement in Tännikon was done in quantiAGREMI A1.5.2.

3.4 Tracer Dispersion Method and Inverse dispersion modelling

CH_4 and NH_3 emissions from agricultural sources with complex and spatially distributed emission areas (e.g., housing, manure storage, exercise yards) can be quantified using a combination of mobile plume measurements, tracer gas release, and inverse dispersion modelling. This methodology integrates high-precision gas measurements, meteorological observations, and Gaussian dispersion modelling, and is well suited for whole-farm assessments under appropriate weather and topographic conditions.

3.4.1 Measurement Setup

In our case, plume concentration measurements were conducted using a mobile Tunable Infrared Laser Direct Absorption Spectroscopy (TILDAS) system and an open-path ammonia gas analyzer, both mounted on a vehicle. The TILDAS system continuously recorded concentrations of CH_4 , N_2O , CO_2 , and H_2O at a 1 Hz sampling rate, while NH_3 concentrations were measured at a 10 Hz sampling rate using the open-path analyzer. Ambient air was sampled at approximately 3 meters above ground level from the front of the vehicle as it drove along transects perpendicular to the wind direction, 200 to 1000 meters downwind of the farm.

Meteorological data, including wind speed, direction, and turbulence, were collected using a 3D sonic anemometer operating at 10 Hz , placed in an open area near the measurement location to avoid interference from nearby obstacles. All datasets were synchronized and merged into 1 Hz interval data after applying a correction for the TILDAS system delay (~ 5 seconds), caused by the short inlet line.

3.4.1.1 Tracer Dispersion Method (TDM)

A known emission rate of N_2O (tracer gas) was released from a calibrated gas cylinder placed near the farm site. The tracer release location was chosen based on wind direction and site accessibility, and aimed to mimic the dispersion characteristics of the target gas (e.g., CH_4 or NH_3). When tracer and target gas plumes are assumed to disperse similarly, the emission rate of the target gas is calculated as:

$$Q_{source} = Q_{tracer} \cdot \frac{M_{source}}{M_{tracer}} \cdot \frac{\int S_{source}}{\int S_{tracer}}$$

Where:

Q_{source} : emission rate of the target gas (g/s);

Q_{tracer} : known emission rate of the tracer (g/s);

M_{source} and M_{tracer} : molar mass of the source gas and the tracer gas (g/mol);

This method provides a direct quantification approach, especially useful when a dispersion model is not applicable due to source complexity.

3.4.1.2 Inverse Dispersion Modelling (IDM)

A Gaussian dispersion model (figure 3) is typically used to estimate concentration fields when the source emission rate is known. Here, the model is applied inversely, to estimate emission rates based on measured concentration data and meteorological conditions. When tracer data were available, the model was calibrated to observed tracer plumes, improving its accuracy for the target gas. In such cases, CH_4 or NH_3 emissions were estimated by comparing the measured plume profile with that generated by the model:

$$Q_{meas} = Q_{model} \cdot \frac{\int S_{meas}}{\int S_{model}}$$

Where:

Q_{meas} : calculated emission rate of the target gas (in g/s);

Q_{model} : modelled reference emission rate (e.g., 1 g/s);

$\int S_{meas}$ and $\int S_{model}$: integrated plume signal (measured or modelled) (in ppbv).

Figure 3. Schematic image of the plume behaviour used for Gaussian Plume modelling

Model inputs included:

- Distance between source and transect
- Wind speed and direction
- Surface roughness and terrain
- Atmospheric stability (classified using Pasquill stability classes A to G)

3.4.2 Measurement Conditions and Constraints

Both methods require stable meteorological conditions to ensure accurate emission estimates. Specifically, wind speeds should range between 2 and 12 m/s, with a consistent wind direction and the availability of a clear measurement transect oriented perpendicular to the wind. Wind speeds below 2 m/s can result in poorly defined plumes and increased uncertainty, while speeds above 12 m/s may cause excessive dilution, reducing the ability to detect low emissions. In areas with complex terrain or nearby obstacles, longer measurement distances are necessary to adequately capture the representative plume. Further there must be no other sources of emissions in the vicinity. N₂O can only be used as a tracer gas if there are no other significant sources of N₂O present.

3.4.3 Uncertainty and Validation

Several sources of uncertainty were considered in the emission quantification process, including instrument noise and calibration drift, short-term variations in wind direction, fluctuations in background gas concentrations, and natural variability in emission levels. To quantify these uncertainties, standard deviation and standard error were calculated from repeated plume measurements. Conducting multiple plume transects was found to reduce uncertainty significantly.

Uncertainty calculations were performed using the existing dataset collected at the Dutch Middenmeer farm during a two-day measurement campaign in October 2024 in the framework of quantiAGREMI A1.5.4 (see Zhang et al., 2025). The core methodology was the TDM, which involves releasing a known quantity of tracer gas (N₂O) and determining emission rates of the target gases by comparing their dispersion patterns with that of the tracer. This approach was implemented during two campaign days at the dairy farm; however, only the results from the first day are included in the report. Short-term wind direction shifts (5–10 min) are a key source of variation in emission estimates (Fredenslund et al., 2019). Emission rates and downwind concentrations also vary with meteorological factors such as wind speed, temperature, inversion height, and solar radiation.

Mobile measurement studies show that multiple downwind transects significantly reduce uncertainty, as relative error decreases exponentially with the number of detected plumes (Hensen et al., 2018). Around six plumes provide an optimal balance between accuracy and effort. Consistent with other findings (Luetschwager et al., 2019; 2021; Maazalahi et al., 2022), plume variability between transects can increase uncertainty, but averaging multiple passes mitigates this.

3.4.4 Examples

The use of inverse Gaussian dispersion modelling combined with tracer release has been widely validated as an effective method for quantifying emissions from diffuse and spatially distributed sources, such as agricultural facilities and landfills (Czepiel et al., 1996; Hensen & Scharff, 2001; Fredenslund et al., 2019). When tracer gases like N₂O are released at known rates, they can be used to calibrate dispersion models, thereby improving the accuracy of emission estimates for target gases such as CH₄ and NH₃ (Hensen, 2012). This is only possible if there are no other sources of N₂O. A methodological comparison was conducted between an inverse dispersion modelling method and the external tracer ratio method under Swiss conditions, which are characterised by lower wind speeds and more complex

topography by Bühler et al. (2021) and Valach et al. (2023). These comparisons showed that the agreement of the absolute values after correcting the inverse dispersion modelling values was satisfactory. However, very long measurement periods are necessary to obtain reliable data using this method. Periods with low wind speeds at night, especially in summer, cannot be used and thus can lead to a systematic bias.

The inverse dispersion modelling approach is particularly useful under stable meteorological conditions, as low wind speeds ($< 2 \text{ m}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$) or highly variable wind directions can significantly increase uncertainty by disrupting plume transport (Fredenslund et al., 2019; Maazallahi et al., 2022). Furthermore, multiple downwind transects have been shown to reduce the uncertainty of emission estimates, with six transects identified as an optimal balance between accuracy and operational effort (Luetschwager et al., 2021).

3.5 Simplified method

The “Simplified Method” (Hassouna et al., 2016) has been developed by IDELE and INRAE to identify field variability of GHG and NH_3 emissions in dairy barns and adapted to other productions. It has been designed to be used by non-expert people and at low cost. Within the CCCFarming project, the result presentation has been improved to help farmers and stakeholders involved in mitigation strategies to manage their emission reductions and the refinement of emission factors or categories based on an extensive field survey (<https://cccfarming.eu/results/wp-outputs-deliveries/files/wp1/Annexes.pdf>).

It relies on two main assumptions:

- the majority of volatilized carbon is emitted in the form of CO_2 . The method cannot be implemented when there is no animal (or another known source of CO_2) inside the barn.
- under stable livestock production and manure storage conditions, ammonia and greenhouse gas emissions are proportional to CO_2 emissions.

This method combines the mass balance approach for estimating carbon losses from the building with the concentration differences of key gases (NH_3 , N_2O , CH_4 , CO_2 , H_2O) between indoor and outdoor (figure 4).

Carbon losses are calculated either with data collated from the farmer (highest Tier of the method) either with reference data when no data are available (lowest tier of the method) or not consistent (e.g. feed quantity too high or too low considering the requirements of animal production).

To determine gas concentrations, average air samples from inside and outside the building are collected in sampling bags. Gas concentrations are then measured either directly on-site or later in a laboratory (see video “Gas measurement” <https://cccfarming.eu/videos>).

Mass balances for nitrogen (N), phosphorus (P), potassium (K), and water can be used to verify the consistency and reliability of the results when specific data of the farm are available. The P and K balances serve to assess the overall quality of the mass balance calculations. The N balance is used to evaluate the plausibility of the calculated emissions of nitrogen compounds (N_2O and NH_3 ; these emissions cannot be higher than the nitrogen losses, given the uncertainties of these estimates). When the water input of the barn can be estimated, the water balance helps ensure that air samples are representative and that the mass balance data are valid.

Figure 4. Calculating emissions based on gas concentrations and farm data (from Hassouna et al., 2016)

3.5.1 Measurement Setup

The simplified method has been implemented during the quantiAGREMI project (A1.5.2). The experimental site was the experimental dairy housing of Agroscope in Aadorf (Switzerland). This site has been designed to provide state-of-the-art emission measurements (dual tracer-ratio method using external tracer gases, see also 3.3) of two identical animal groups kept in two separate experimental compartments, representative of commercial dairy barns, where different treatments can be implemented (Mohn et al., 2018). The emissions of CO₂, CH₄ and NH₃ were compared to the results obtained with the external tracer-ratio method and the CO₂ balance method with CO₂ estimated with DIN 18910. The comparison took place in September 2024, between 11th at 10h00 and 12th at 23h00 pm. The milking periods (morning between 5h30 and 7h00 and afternoon between 16h30 and 18h00) were discarded for calculation of average emissions. The reference emissions were measured continuously (10 min time step alternatively in both compartments) during this period while the emissions deduced from CO₂ balance or simplified method were deduced from spot air sampling on September 11th (10h – 13h) and on 12th (10h – 13h and 14h – 16h).

The two animal groups only differed by feeding (hay or silage). The live weights were measured individually on 10th and 17th September. The median of the differences in live weights between both measurements was considered as the uncertainty on observed average live weights. The milk productions (milk yield, fat, protein and urea contents) of the cows were measured individually on afternoon of 11th September and morning of September 12th. The medians of the differences between both measurements were considered as the uncertainty on observed averages per compartment. The fat corrected milk (FCM, cf. Annex 1) was used as “milk production” in DIN 18910. DIN 18910 also accounts for the influence of

temperature on heat production. Finally, it proposes to use $0.200 \text{ (L_CO}_2 \text{ animal}^{-1}) \text{ W}^{-1}$ to convert estimates of heat production into CO_2 emission. We used the same uncertainty as given in Annex 1 ($0.015 \text{ (L_CO}_2 \text{ animal}^{-1}) \text{ W}^{-1}$). The floor was scraped twelve times a day. Straw (around 0.54 kg per cow and per day) was used as bedding material for the cubicles. The cows went on pasture during the night (after afternoon milking, 21h and until morning milking, 5h30).

Spot sampling of the air was done outside the barn, upwind and downwind, and inside the barn at two levels (around 0.5 m and 2 m above the floor, Figure 5). The air was collected during the morning of September 11th, in the morning and afternoon of September 12th. Two SKC air sampling pumps were connected to Flexfoil® bags with tygon tubes and PTFE $0.2 \mu\text{m}$ syringe filters. The air flow rate was adjusted to sample air during around 10 minutes while walking continuously in all places of each compartment. Sampling was done before and after floor scraping. Gas concentrations were analysed with GC for CO_2 , CH_4 and N_2O , after sampling the bag in tubes, and with Draeger tubes (2/a) for NH_3 , directly on the bags. A total of five bags were collected inside the barn. Three bags were collected outside the barn, upwind, 1 bag each half day (around 20 minutes time difference between sampling time inside and outside). The bags collected outside downwind were discarded because their NH_3 concentrations were systematically higher than upwind. Using these concentrations significantly decreased the gradient between inside and outside and would have induced an underestimation of emissions.

Figure 5. sampling air inside the barn

The uncertainty sources considered were the live weight (kg cow^{-1}), the feed intake ($\text{kg_DM cow}^{-1} \text{ day}^{-1}$), the number of grazing hours, the bedding input ($\text{kg_straw cow}^{-1} \text{ day}^{-1}$), the milk production ($\text{L_milk day}^{-1} \text{ cow}^{-1}$) and its fat (g L^{-1}) content, the outdoor temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$), the gas concentrations (N_2O , CO_2 , NH_3 , CH_4) and the ratio between gradients of CO_2 and CH_4 ($\text{Grad C-CO}_2 / \text{Grad C-CH}_4$). For the simplified method, the uncertainty was calculated using a Monte-Carlo approach and the uncertainty sources were ranked using the Spearman correlation between ranks. For the reference method, the variability of measurements (standard deviation of the 10 min measurements for the 3 hours estimate or of the 24 hours averages starting on 11th from 10h to 23h) was considered as the uncertainty.

3.5.2 Results

The quasi-continuous measurements with the dual tracer-ratio method shows that the CO_2 emission almost stops during the night (grazing time) while the emissions of NH_3 and CH_4 continue to a lesser extent. The emission of N_2O was not detected but the detection level was probably too high (N losses through N_2O were expected to be under 10 % of N losses through NH_3), given the high ventilation rate. The uncertainty of the dual tracer-ratio method is within 3-10 % (Mohn et al., 2018). Table 3 shows that extrapolating the hourly emissions to the day on a time basis (hourly emission during 14h and no emissions during 10h) induce a bias around 10% underestimation. As a matter of fact, manure is a source of all these gases since the house is not completely clean during the grazing time. Further a daily emission variation due to several factors (e.g. temperature, animal activity, management aspects) is expected.

Table 3: reference emissions: results of average emission measurements with the dual-tracer ratio method ($\text{g_gas day}^{-1} \text{cow}^{-1}$; grazing time 21h – 5h30; milking periods 16h30 – 18h and 5h30 – 7h)

Observation	CO ₂		CH ₄		NH ₃	
	North	South	North	South	North	South
September 11 th 10h – 13h	11830 ± 234	13286 ± 280	919 ± 57	798 ± 21	55 ± 5	62 ± 3
September 12 th 10h – 13h	12113 ± 804	14156 ± 601	587 ± 47	740 ± 27	52 ± 1	67 ± 2
September 12 th 13h – 16h	13358 ± 535	14980 ± 279	687 ± 46	801 ± 41	53 ± 3	58 ± 7
24 h average (20 cows present from 7h to 21h)	8082 ± 384	9132 ± 356	565 ± 53	673 ± 17	35 ± 1	42 ± 2
24h extrapolation from hourly observation (14h presence in the house)	7253 ± 474	8249 ± 494	426 ± 99	455 ± 20	31 ± 1	36 ± 2

The CO₂ emission estimated with DIN 18910 depends on live weight, milk production, fat content of milk and pregnancy (cf. Annex 1). Input data and results are given in Table 4. Results of protein content and urea were not used but are mentioned for potential use with other methods and interpretations. Outside temperature varied between 6 and 18 °C. During the spot samplings, temperatures inside the barn were between 13 and 15 °C, around 1 K above outside temperature, due to high wind and ventilation. To estimate the influence of temperature on CO₂ emission during 24 hours, we used the outside average and an uncertainty of 5 K to have the potential influence of this factor on the precision of predicted CO₂ emission.

CO₂ emissions predicted by the CO₂ model include the reference emission measured with the dual-tracer method. Moreover, the observed higher CO₂ emission in barn North is predicted from the higher live weight and milk production observed. The higher urea content observed in milk from compartment North does not correspond to an observed higher NH₃ emission (Table 3). The uncertainty predicted in this case is lower than the figure given in Annex 1. It is mainly due to the lower uncertainty on both live weight and pregnancy.

Table 4: observed averages and animal scale variability in live weight and milk production of cows and CO₂ emissions deduced with DIN 18910 ($\text{g CO}_2 \text{day}^{-1} \text{cow}^{-1}$; 14 hours day^{-1} presence of cows in the house)

	North	South
Live weight of cows (kg cow^{-1}) (uncertainty: 21 kg cow^{-1})	683 ± 56	693 ± 70

	North	South
Milk production (L_milk day ⁻¹ cow ⁻¹) (uncertainty: 2.1 L_milk day ⁻¹ cow ⁻¹)	26.9 ± 7.8	30.5 ± 6.7
Fat content (g_fat L ⁻¹) (uncertainty: 7.2 g_fat L ⁻¹)	42.0 ± 5.5	45.6 ± 6.1
Protein content (g_protein L ⁻¹) (uncertainty: 0.7 g_protein L ⁻¹)	34.3 ± 3.3	35.5 ± 3.3
Urea content (mg_urea L ⁻¹) (uncertainty: 40 mg_urea L ⁻¹)	240 ± 80	173 ± 51
Pregnancy (days) (uncertainty: 40 days)	assumed 150 ± 40	
Outside temperature (°C) (uncertainty: 5 K)	10.5 ± 2.8	
Daily CO ₂ emission (g_CO ₂ day ⁻¹ cow ⁻¹) (uncertainty with Monte-Carlo method)	12731 ± 1316	13951 ± 1418
Housing CO ₂ emission whith 10 h grazing (g_CO ₂ day ⁻¹ cow ⁻¹) (uncertainty with Monte-Carlo method)	7427 ± 768	8138 ± 827

Additional input used with the simplified method are given in Table 5 and measured emissions in Table 6.

The comparison of CO₂ emissions measured with the simplified method shows higher uncertainties than with the CO₂ balance method. However, the bias is below 10%. The emissions of NH₃ are in the same range as those predicted with the reference method but the low precision does not allow to observe the small difference between barns observed with the reference method. Regarding the CH₄ emission, the figures measured with the simplified method are similar to those deduced from hourly observations (14 hours presence of cows in the house) and underestimate the “true” value observed with the dual tracer-ratio method, including observations when the cows are grazing, outside the house.

The overall uncertainty of emissions measured with the simplified method was around 50 % for the different gases. This high value was mainly due to the high ventilation inducing small concentration differences between outside and inside and a higher sensitivity of results to small variations in gas concentrations. The influence of following input variables on emission uncertainty was studied with Spearman’s rank correlation method: live weight, feed intake, hours grazing, bedding input, milk production, fat content, protein content, outdoor temperature, gradients of CO₂, CH₄ and NH₃ between outside and inside and the ratio Grad C-CO₂ / Grad C-CH₄. Results of the main influencing variables are given in Table 7. The ranking of uncertainties shows the primary importance of grazing time, feed intake and gas concentrations in measuring emissions specific of one housing.

Table 5: additional observations used in the simplified method to measure ammonia and greenhouse gases and observed emissions ($\text{g}_{\text{gas}} \text{day}^{-1} \text{cow}^{-1}$; 14 hours day^{-1} presence of cows in the house)

	Outside	North	South
Total feed intake ($\text{kg}_{\text{DM}} \text{cow}^{-1} \text{day}^{-1}$) (uncertainty: 0.1 kg DM / 100 kg live weight cow^{-1})	-	21.8 \pm 1.4	22.5 \pm 1.8
Bedding input ($\text{kg}_{\text{straw}} \text{cow}^{-1} \text{day}^{-1}$) (uncertainty: 20 % bedding input)	-	0.54 \pm 0.1	0.54 \pm 0.1
September 11 th 10h – 13h			
CO ₂ concentrations (ppm) (uncertainty: 10 ppm)	421	432 (2 m) 440 (0.5m)	- (2 m) 457 (0.5m)
CH ₄ concentrations (ppm) (uncertainty: 1 ppm)	4.3	4.0 (2 m) 5.3 (0.5m)	- (2 m) 7.0 (0.5m)
NH ₃ concentrations (ppm) (uncertainty: 0,05 ppm)	0.0	0.20 (2 m) 0.30 (0.5m)	- (2 m) 0.3 (0.5m)
N ₂ O concentrations (ppm) (uncertainty: 0,003 ppm)	0.347	0.347 (2 m) 0.350 (0.5m)	- (2 m) 0.345 (0.5m)
September 12 th 10h – 13h			
CO ₂ concentrations (ppm) (uncertainty: 10 ppm)	435	453 (2 m) 484 (0.5m)	465 (2 m) 521 (0.5m)
CH ₄ concentrations (ppm) (uncertainty: 1 ppm)	2.2	5.9 (2 m) 9.6 (0.5m)	9.3 (2 m) 18.6 (0.5m)
NH ₃ concentrations (ppm) (uncertainty: 0,05 ppm)	0.0	0.20 (2 m) 0.30 (0.5m)	0.3 (2 m) 0.5 (0.5m)
N ₂ O concentrations (ppm) (uncertainty: 0,003 ppm)	0.354	0.343 (2 m) 0.347 (0.5m)	0.348 (2 m) 0.353 (0.5m)
September 12 th 13h – 16h			
CO ₂ concentrations (ppm) (uncertainty: 10 ppm)	425	489 (2 m)	491 (2 m)
CH ₄ concentrations (ppm) (uncertainty: 1 ppm)	2.7	9.0 (2 m)	9.3 (2 m)

	Outside	North	South
NH ₃ concentrations (ppm) (uncertainty: 0,05 ppm)	0.0	0.3 (2 m)	0.4 (2 m)
N ₂ O concentrations (ppm) (uncertainty: 0,003 ppm)	0.351	0.353 (2 m)	0.352 (2 m)

Table 6: emissions measured with the simplified method ($\text{g}_{\text{gas}} \text{day}^{-1} \text{cow}^{-1}$; 14h presence of cows in the house; uncertainties calculated using Monte-Carlo method with additional uncertainties of 20% on concentration gradient and 2 hours on grazing time)

	North	South
September 11 th 10h – 13h		
Housing CO ₂ emission ($\text{g}_{\text{CO}_2} \text{day}^{-1} \text{cow}^{-1}$)	9038 ± 1262 (2 m) 9413 ± 1310 (0.5m)	- (2 m) 9490 ± 1267 (0.5m)
Housing CH ₄ emission ($\text{g}_{\text{CH}_4} \text{day}^{-1} \text{cow}^{-1}$)	301 ± 99 (2 m) 174 ± 31 (0.5m)	- (2 m) 253 ± 45 (0.5m)
Housing NH ₃ emission ($\text{g}_{\text{NH}_3} \text{day}^{-1} \text{cow}^{-1}$)	57 ± 21 (2 m) 62 ± 26 (0.5m)	- (2 m) 32 ± 9 (0.5m)
Housing N ₂ O emission ($\text{g}_{\text{N}_2\text{O}} \text{day}^{-1} \text{cow}^{-1}$)	2 ± 1 (2 m) 2 ± 1 (0.5m)	- (2 m) 1 ± 0 (0.5m)
September 12 th 10h – 13h		
Housing CO ₂ emission ($\text{g}_{\text{CO}_2} \text{day}^{-1} \text{cow}^{-1}$)	8268 ± 1154 (2 m) 8554 ± 1206 (0.5m)	8208 ± 1102 (2 m) 8568 ± 1230 (0.5m)
Housing CH ₄ emission ($\text{g}_{\text{CH}_4} \text{day}^{-1} \text{cow}^{-1}$)	640 ± 117 (2 m) 479 ± 85 (0.5m)	723 ± 129 (2 m) 607 ± 114 (0.5m)
Housing NH ₃ emission ($\text{g}_{\text{NH}_3} \text{day}^{-1} \text{cow}^{-1}$)	40 ± 17 (2 m) 21 ± 5 (0.5m)	33 ± 10 (2 m) 20 ± 5 (0.5m)
Housing N ₂ O emission ($\text{g}_{\text{N}_2\text{O}} \text{day}^{-1} \text{cow}^{-1}$)	2 ± 1 (2 m) 1 ± 0 (0.5m)	1 ± 0 (2 m) 0 ± 0 (0.5m)
September 12 th 13h – 16h		
Housing CO ₂ emission ($\text{g}_{\text{CO}_2} \text{day}^{-1} \text{cow}^{-1}$)	9085 ± 1270 (2 m)	9262 ± 1282 (2 m)
Housing CH ₄ emission ($\text{g}_{\text{CH}_4} \text{day}^{-1} \text{cow}^{-1}$)	325 ± 57 (2 m)	338 ± 59 (2 m)
Housing NH ₃ emission ($\text{g}_{\text{NH}_3} \text{day}^{-1} \text{cow}^{-1}$)	17 ± 4 (2 m)	22 ± 5 (2 m)
Housing N ₂ O emission ($\text{g}_{\text{N}_2\text{O}} \text{day}^{-1} \text{cow}^{-1}$)	0 ± 0 (2 m)	0 ± 0 (2 m)
Average from all repetitions		

	North	South
Housing CO ₂ emission (g_CO ₂ day ⁻¹ cow ⁻¹)	9261 ± 3854	9290 ± 3969
Housing CH ₄ emission (g_CH ₄ day ⁻¹ cow ⁻¹)	379 ± 181	475 ± 214
Housing NH ₃ emission (g_NH ₃ day ⁻¹ cow ⁻¹)	37.2 ± 21.6	26.8 ± 11.0
Housing N ₂ O emission (g_N ₂ O day ⁻¹ cow ⁻¹)	1.32 ± 0.96	0.64 ± 0.34

Beside these influences on the precision of results, other processes can influence the trueness of emissions. Comparison with the dual-tracer ratio method showed that emissions of manure in the absence of animals can induce a bias in the estimate with the simplified method. The protocol used to measure gas concentrations can also induce bias in the measurement of concentration gradients (sampling representativeness, e.g. when sampling outside air downwind will reduce the observed concentration gradient; calibration, response time and sensitivity of gas analysers). Finally, when the input data result from farmer indications, the biological variables mentioned in DIN 18910 can also influence the trueness: they influence the heat production of animals (live weight, milk production, and days in pregnancy, in the case of dairy cows) and consequently their feed intake and their CO₂ emission.

Table 7: main input data influencing the uncertainty of CO₂, CH₄ and NH₃ emissions

variable	rank	correlation
influence on CO ₂ uncertainty		
nb hours grazing	1	-0,273
DM feed intake	2	0,263
Grad C-CO ₂ / Grad C-CH ₄	3	0,245
Fat content of milk	4	0,075
Bedding input	5	0,069
influence on CH ₄ uncertainty		
Grad C-CO ₂ / Grad C-CH ₄	1	-0,666
DM feed intake	2	0,185
nb hours grazing	3	-0,124
Grad CO ₂	4	0,066
Fat content of milk	5	0,054
influence on NH ₃ uncertainty		
Grad CO ₂	1	-0,794
Grad NH ₃	2	0,404
Grad C-CO ₂ / Grad C-CH ₄	3	0,109
DM feed intake	4	0,102

nb hours grazing	5	-0,070
------------------	---	--------

3.5.3 Conclusion

The simplified method has a rather high uncertainty (30-50 %), particularly when the CO₂ gradient between inside and outside is small. Nevertheless, it showed a good repeatability between the two compartments and a flexible capacity to sample air in all parts of the barn, with potentially more or less manure accumulation and emissions. Integrating farm specific data (biological as well as gas concentrations) over a large sample of farming activities and seasons can help to improve representativeness of emission factors. Further simplification of data input, quality checks and quality assurance is required to optimize data selection and improve emission factors on a national scale. The potential bias due to emissions of manure in the absence of animals should be considered when evaluating uncertainties.

4 Decision matrix

The decision matrix summarises (figure 6) the methodological approaches described in Chapter 2 and the measurement methods described in Chapter 3. Different measurement approaches and methods should be applied depending on the purpose and conditions. This step-by-step decision matrix can be used to select the most suitable measurement approaches and methods, taking into account the ventilation system, the system to be determined and the system boundaries. Furthermore, the uncertainty of the measurement method is also a criterion.

Figure 6. Decision matrix for selecting the appropriate approach and method for determining emissions depending on the purpose and ventilation system

For example, a case-control approach is necessary to develop and quantify new mitigation measures (e.g. slurry additives, feeding strategies, floor types). This can involve taking measurements in two housing compartments simultaneously. In a naturally ventilated housing, this can only be achieved using either the external tracer ratio method or the CO₂ balancing method. Inverse dispersion modelling or the tracer inverse method are not suitable because they cover the entire farm and cannot differentiate between housing compartments. However, the uncertainties of the simplified method are too high to reliably determine the reduction potential.

5 Further measurement requirements

5.1 Requirements for measurement devices and set-ups to quantify gas concentrations

Measurements in livestock housings are challenging for the analytics and the sampling setup, because of spectral interferences with water, adsorption of NH_3 on surfaces (filters, lines, inlet of spectrometer) and the presence of particles, which have to be efficiently removed without NH_3 interference. Within the quantiAGREMI project different tubing and filter materials as well as analyzer coatings have been tested (see A1.3.3). In general, spectral interferences of H_2O and other trace gases on target analysis by commercial CRDS analyzers may occur and were studied in A1.3.2.

Additionally, in common naturally ventilated housing systems with large openings, the amount fractions of target gases (NH_3 , CH_4 , CO_2 , N_2O , etc.) are near to ambient and thus, the gradients to air outside of the housing are very small. In contrast to naturally ventilated housings, the amount fractions could be much higher in mechanically ventilated housings. Linearity and repeatability of commercial analyzers over relevant concentration ranges were tested in the quantiAGREMI project, e.g. in A1.3.1. When temporal variations of concentrations occur outside the house due to changes in sources (e.g. photosynthesis during the day and respiration of plants during the night; changes in wind direction), the time lag between the concentration peak outside and the corresponding concentration peak inside depends on the ventilation rate and its homogeneity inside the house.

Furthermore, both the selection of sampling points for a representative measurement and the protection of sampling points from the animals are important. Adequacy of the implemented sampling strategy for representative sampling and homogeneous mixing can be tested in a validation study, dosing known amounts of the target gas into the animal housing and comparing quantified and expected emission fluxes (Mohn et al., 2018). A simpler option would be to use smoke tests to visually demonstrate the airflow under different wind and ventilation conditions.

5.2 Collection of relevant accompanying parameters

In addition to the measurement approach and gas analytics, the collection of accompanying parameters in parallel with the measurements is essential. Information on the measurement situation, e.g., meteorological parameters, or details on the housing system, management, animals and feeding, etc. are often incomplete or missing (Poteko et al., 2018; Vigan et al., 2019). Accompanying parameters describe a specific measurement situation, providing information on the housing system, animals, feeding, manure removal, management and climate (Table 8). Complete information on area, stocking rate, breed, climatic conditions, feed and yield is essential when comparing emission values between farms, housing systems, country-specific characteristics and different studies. Emission data can be checked for plausibility and compared within a farm over time as well as between farms by using accompanying parameters (wind speed, special events, management, animal activity, etc.). Indoor (and outdoor) wind speed can cause concentration dilution of the target gas. Depending on the measurement and analysis methods, parameters such as temperature, relative humidity and barometric pressure may be required to standardize the analytical values. In order to correct the measured target gas concentration in the housing, the site-specific background concentration recording is essential. Parameters such as area, number of animals, livestock units or milk yield and time designations must be recorded as fully as possible as reference units. These allow comparisons between different studies. Relevant variables affecting emissions must be identified and quantified in order to model emissions, to perform meta-analyses and derive mitigation measures. The recording of accompanying parameters must be matched in time and space to the target value as well as to the purpose of the measurements. Accompanying parameters are also useful to convert emissions values in different units in order to extend their utilization to different targets (Webb et al., 2021).

Table 8. Different functions and examples of accompanying parameters (modified from Schrade et al., 2011)

Function of accompanying parameters	Examples of accompanying parameters
Characterisation of the measuring situation	Area, stocking rate, animal activity, climate, management, exercise area soiling, N content in feed, urea and slurry, crude fibre content in feed, feed intake, etc.
Plausibility of target gas concentration	Air speed at sampling locations, special events, etc.
Standardisation of measuring values (target gas)	Temperature, relative atmospheric humidity, air pressure, etc.
Adjustment of target gas concentration	Background concentration
Reference units for emission data	Area, number of animals, livestock units, weight gain, milk yield, time, etc.
Influencing variables on emissions	Temperature, air speed, management, exercise area soiling, N content in feed, urea and slurry, crude fibre content in feed, feed intake, etc.

5.3 Data processing and statistical analysis

Depending on the target gas, the measuring device used and the conditions, the measured values must be corrected. This may involve standardising to a specific temperature or air pressure, and/or correcting for background concentration. Further, a plausibility check must be performed. Therefore, the data is visualised in order to identify and exclude invalid data resulting from sensor malfunctions or atypical measurement conditions, as well as to explore correlations among the measured variables. This is followed by a systematic assessment of data quality and outlier treatment, focusing on handling anomalies not attributable to instrument failure or extreme conditions. Statistical methods are then applied to perform quantitative analyses, culminating in standardized emission value reporting. The choice of experimental unit is important here. Autocorrelations and time lags should also be investigated. Depending on the purpose and measurement approach, random effects (e.g. measurement day, season, animal, farm) can also be included in the statistics alongside explanatory effects (e.g. temperature, treatment, etc.), thus providing information about their impact on emissions. Comprehensive methodologies for data processing are detailed on the VERA website (<https://www.vera-verification.eu/test-protocols/>), Robin et al. (2010) and Hassouna et al. (2023).

6 References

- Berry, N.R., Zeyer, K., Emmenegger, L. & Keck, M., 2005: Emissionen von Staub (PM10) und Ammoniak (NH₃) aus traditionellen und neuen Stallsystemen mit Untersuchungen im Bereich der Mastschweinehaltung. Agroscope FAT Tänikon, Ettenhausen und Empa, Dübendorf, p. 108
- Bobrowski, A.B., Willink, D., Janke, D., Amon, T., Hagenkamp-Korth, F., Hasler, M., & Hartung, E., 2021: Reduction of ammonia emissions by applying a urease inhibitor in naturally ventilated dairy barns. *Biosystems Engineering* (204), 104-114. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biosystemseng.2021.01.011>
- Bobrowski, A.B., Van Dooren, H.J., Ogink, N.W.M., Hagenkamp-Korth, F., Hasler, M. & Hartung, E., 2021: Reduction of ammonia emissions by using a urease inhibitor in a mechanically ventilated dairy housing system. *Biosystems Engineering* (204), 115-129. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biosystemseng.2021.01.006>
- Bühler, M., Häni, C., Ammann, C., Mohn, J., Neftel, A., Schrade, S., Zähler, M., Zeyer, K., Brönnimann, S. & Kupper, T., 2021: Assessment of the inverse dispersion method for the determination of methane emissions from a dairy housing. *Agricultural and Forest Meteorology*, 307, 2021, 1-10. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agrformet.2021.108501>
- Burns, R.T., Li, H., Xin, H., Gates, R.S., Overhults, D.G., Earnest, J. & Beal Moody, L., 2008. Greenhouse Gas (GHG) Emissions from Broiler Houses in the Southeastern United States, 2008 Providence, Rhode Island, June 29 – July 2, 2008. ASABE, St. Joseph, MI.
- Coorevits, K.R.P., Declerck, A., Van Overbeke, P., Janke, D., Vandenbussche, C., Norton, T., Demeyer, P. & Brusselman, E., 2025: Development of a direct measuring method for determining air flow rates in naturally ventilated dairy barns with ventilation screens. *Submitted to Biosystems Engineering*.
- Czepiel, P.M., Mosher, B., Harriss, C., Shorter, J.H., McManus, J.B., Kolb, C. E., Allewine, E. & Lamb, B.K., 1996. Landfill methane emissions measured by enclosure and atmospheric tracer methods, *J. Geophys Res.* 101, 16711-16719.
- DIN 18910:2017-08. Thermal insulation for closed livestock buildings - Thermal insulation and ventilation - Principles for planning and design for closed ventilated livestock buildings. <https://dx.doi.org/10.31030/2680106>
- Edouard, N., Mosquera, J., Van Dooren, H.J.C., Mendes, L.B. & Ogink, N.W.M., 2016: Comparison of CO₂ and SF₆ based tracer gas methods for the estimation of ventilation rates in a naturally ventilated dairy barn. *Biosystems Engineering* (149), 11-23. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.biosystemseng.2016.06.001>
- Fredenslund, A.M., Rees-White, T.C., Beaven, R.P., Delre, A., Finlayson, A., Helmore, J., Allen, G. & Scheutz, C., 2019. Validation and error assessment of the mobile tracer gas dispersion method for measurement of fugitive emissions from area sources. *Waste Management*, 83: 68-78.
- Hassouna, M., Amon, T., Arcidiacono, C., Bühler, M., Calvet, S., Demeyer, P., D'Urso, P.R., Estellés, F., Häni, C., Hempel, S., Janke, D., Kjosevski, M., Kupper, T., Mohn, J., Mosquera, J., Norton, T., Scheutz, C., Thygesen Vechi N., Van Overbeke, P., & Schrade, S., 2023. Measuring techniques for ammonia and greenhouse gas emissions from naturally ventilated housings. In: *Technology for environmentally friendly livestock production*. Editor: Thomas Bartzanas, Springer. 23-63. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-19730-7_3
- Hassouna, M., Eglin, T., Cellier, P., Colomb, V., Cohan, J.P., et al., 2016. Measuring emissions from livestock farming: greenhouse gases, ammonia and nitrogen oxides. INRA-ADEME, 2016, ISBN 2-7380-1392-9. <https://hal.science/hal-01567208v1>
- Hensen, A. and Scharff, H., 2001. Methane emission estimates from landfills obtained with dynamic plume measurements. *Water Air Soil Pollut.* 1 455–64 (Focus)
- Hensen, A., 2012. Methods for observation and quantification of trace gas emissions from diffuse sources. *PhD Thesis VU Amsterdam*.
- Hensen, A., Velzeboer, I., Van Dinther, D., Van den Bulk, W.C.M. & Frumau, K.F.A., 2018. Berekening van methaanemissies van een geselecteerd aantal actieve gaswinningslocaties voor Staatstoezicht op de Mijnen. *TNO 2019 R10332*, TNO Petten.
- Hensen, A., Velzeboer, I., Frumau, K.F.A., Van den Bulk, W.C.M. & Van Dinther, D., 2019. Methane emission measurements of offshore oil and gas platforms. *TNO report R10895*, TNO Petten.

- IPCC, 2019. Refinement to the 2006 IPCC Guidelines for National Greenhouse Gas Inventories Volume 4 Agriculture, Forestry and Other Land Use; https://www.ipcc-nggip.iges.or.jp/public/2019rf/pdf/4_Volume4/19R_V4_Ch10_Livestock.pdf
- Luetschwager, E., von Fischer, J. C., Weller, Z. D., Characterizing detection probabilities of advanced mobile leak surveys: Implications for sampling effort and leak size estimation in natural gas distribution systems. *Elementa: Science of the Anthropocene*, 9 (1): 00143. <https://doi.org/10.1525/elementa.2020.00143>, 2021.
- Luostarinen, S., Grönroos, J., Hellstedt, M., Nousiainen, J. & Munther, J., 2017. Finnish Normative Manure System: System Documentation and First Results. *Natural Resources Bioeconomy Studies* 48/2017. Natural Resources Institute Finland, Helsinki. ISBN:978-952-326-443-4. <https://jukuri.luke.fi/items/68ab4421-47d6-4a0e-b000-ee507cb2317c>
- Mohn, J., Zeyer, K., Keck, M., Keller, M., Zähler, M., Poteko, J., Emmenegger, L., & Schrade, S., 2018. A dual tracer ratio method for comparative emission measurements in an experimental dairy housing. *Atmos. Environ.*, 179, 12-22. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.atmosenv.2018.01.057>
- Maazallahi, H., Delre, A., Scheutz, C., Fredenslund, A.M., Schwietzke, S., Denier van der Gon, Hensen, A. & Röckmann, T., 2022. Intercomparison of detection and quantification methods for methane emissions from the natural gas distribution network in Hamburg, Germany, *Atmos. Meas. Tech. Discuss.* [preprint], <https://doi.org/10.5194/amt-2022-134>, in review.
- Ogink, N.W.M., Mosquera, J. & Hol, J.M.G., 2013a. Protocol voor meting van ammoniakemissie uit huisvestingssystemen in de veehouderij 2013. Rapport 726, Wageningen UR Livestock, Lelystad, The Netherlands.
- Ogink, N.W.M., Mosquera, J., Calvet, S. & Zhang, G., 2013b. Methods for measuring gas emissions from naturally ventilated livestock buildings: Developments over the last decade and perspectives for improvement. *Biosystems Engineering* (116), 297-308. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biosystemseng.2012.10.005>
- Phillips, V.R., Lee, D.S., Scholtens, R., Garland, J.A. & Sneath, R.W., 2001. A review of methods for measuring emission rates of ammonia from livestock buildings and slurry or manure stores, Part 2: Monitoring flux rates, concentrations and airflow rates. *Journal of Agricultural Engineering Research*, 78(1), 1-14. <https://doi.org/10.1006/jaer.2000.0618>
- Poteko, J., Zähler, M. & Schrade, S., 2019. Effects of housing system, floor type and temperature on ammonia and methane emissions from dairy farming: A meta-analysis. *Biosystems Engineering* (182), 16-28. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biosystemseng.2019.03.012>
- Robin, P., Amand, Aubert, G. C., Berckmans, D., Cellier, P., Dong, H.M., Durif, M., Hartung, E., Liao, X.D., Nicks, B., Loyon, L. & Powers, W., 2010. Procédure de référence pour la mesure des émissions de polluants gazeux des bâtiments d'élevage et stockages d'effluents d'élevage. *irstea*, pp.519.
- Savanne, D., Arnaud, A., Beneito, A., Berne, P., Burkhalter, R., Cellier, P., Gonze, M.A., Laville, P., Levy, F., Milward, R., Pokryszka, Z., Sabroux, J.C., Tauziède, C. & Tregoures, A., 1997. Comparison of different methods for measuring landfill methane emissions. *Sardinia '97 Sixth International Landfill Symposium*. Vol. IV: 81-85.
- Schiefler, I., 2013. Greenhouse gas and ammonia emissions from dairy barns. VDI-MEG No. 528. Bonn, University of Bonn, p. 84.
- Schrade, S., Keck, M. & Hartung, E., 2011: Accompanying parameters for the measurement of ammonia emissions from dairy cattle housing. *Landtechnik*, 66, (2), 128-131.
- Schrade, S., Zeyer, K., Gygax, L., Emmenegger, L., Hartung, E. & Keck, M., 2012. Ammonia emissions and emission factors of naturally ventilated dairy housing with solid floors and an outdoor exercise area in Switzerland. *Atmospheric Environment* (47), 183–194. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.atmosenv.2011.11.015>
- Schrade, S., Zeyer, K., Mohn, J. & Zähler, M., 2023: Effect of diets with different crude protein levels on ammonia and greenhouse gas emissions from a naturally ventilated dairy housing. *Science of the Total Environment* (896), <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2023.165027>
- Schulte, H., Ammon, C., Hagenkamp-Korth, F. & Hartung, E., 2022. Investigating the time-dependent dose-response relationship of ammonia emissions reduction through the application of a urease inhibitor in pig fattening houses. *Biosystems Engineering* (222), 45-61. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biosystemseng.2022.07.008>

- Schulte, H., Ammon, C., Hagenkamp-Korth, F. & Hartung, E., 2024. Reduction of ammonia emissions in fattening pig houses through the application of a urease inhibitor using different application techniques. *Biosystems Engineering* (247), 42-62. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biosystemseng.2024.08.011>
- Snell, H.G.J., Seipelt, F. & Van den Weghe, H.F.A., 2003. Ventilation rates and gaseous emissions from naturally ventilated dairy houses. *Biosystems Engineering* 86 (1), 67–73. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1537-5110\(03\)00113-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1537-5110(03)00113-2)
- Valach, A. C., Häni, C., Bühler, M., Mohn, J., [Schrade, S.](#) & Kupper, T., 2023. [Ammonia emissions from a dairy housing and wastewater treatment plant quantified with an inverse dispersion method accounting for deposition loss.](#) *Journal of the Air & Waste Management Association*, 73, (12), 2023, 930-950. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10962247.2023.2271426>
- Van Duinkerken, G., Smits, M.C.J., André, G., Šebek, L.B.J. & Dijkstra, J., 2011. Milk urea concentration as an indicator of ammonia emission from dairy cow barn under restricted grazing. *Journal of Dairy Science* 94 (1), 321–335. <https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.2009-2263>
- VERA, 2018: VERA Test Protocol for Livestock Housing and Management Systems, Version 3:2018-09. https://www.vera-verification.eu/app/uploads/sites/9/2019/05/VERA_Testprotocol_Housing_v3_2018.pdf
- Vigan, A., Hassouna, M., Guingand, N., Brame, C., Edouard, N., Eglin, T., Espagnol, S., Eugène, M., Génarmont, S., Lagadec, S., Lorinquer, E., Loyon, L., Ponchant, P. & Robin, P., 2019. Development of a database to collect emission values for Livestock systems. *Journal of Environmental Quality* 48(6), 1899-1906. <https://doi.org/10.2134/jeq2019.01.0007>
- Webb, J., Van der Weerden, T.J., Hassouna, M. & Amon, B., 2021. Guidance on the conversion of gaseous emission units to standardized emission factors and recommendations for data reporting. *Carbon Management* 12: 663-679. [doi:10.1080/17583004.2021.1995502](https://doi.org/10.1080/17583004.2021.1995502).
- Wolf, U., Eurich-Menden, B., Dehler, G., Smirnov & Horlacher, D., 2023. How does an outdoor yard influence ammonia emissions from fattening pig housings. *Agricultural engineering. Eu*, 78(3). <https://doi.org/10.15150/lt.2023.3292>
- Zhang, J., Bronsveld, P.C.P., Hensen, A., Van Mansom, H., Van den Bulk, W.C.M. & Velzeboer, I., 2025. Traceable calibration of open- and closed-path ammonia analyzers using the VSL RGM system and its impact on livestock emission uncertainty. TNO Public Report, R12917, 78 p. <https://publications.tno.nl/publication/34645262/kM5oVotk/TNO-2024-R12917.pdf>

7 Annex 1 - Uncertainty assessment of animal heat and CO₂ production (INRAE, LNE, Agroscope)

(Connected to 3.2 CO₂ Balance method)

This annex presents calculations of uncertainties associated with animal total heat and CO₂ production. The calculations were made using models and knowledge available in the literature and data from past experiments. The results are presented in a manner that ensures complete transparency, and the choices made regarding input values and models can of course be discussed. Nevertheless, beyond any bias in values and models, the methodology is intended to comply with the GUM (2008).

The following equation will be used to calculate the quantity of CO₂ produced by animals in one barn for pig and poultry. For dairy cattle, the quantity of CO₂ production is given for one cow.

$$Q_{CO_2} = \Phi_{Tot} \times CO_{2_{hpu}} \times Nb_{animals} \quad \left(\frac{L_{CO_2}}{h. barn} \right)$$

$CO_{2_{hpu}}$ is given par Pedersen et al., 2008 and will be 0.185 (L animal⁻¹) W⁻¹ for all animal categories.

7.1 Fattening pig

a - Pig total heat production

Concerning pig production, different models are available in literature to calculate the total heat production Φ_{Tot} . Nevertheless, given the progress in animal genetics and animal growth over recent decades, we have chosen to use the most recent model established by Ramirez et al., 2022.

$$\Phi_{Tot} = SC \times LW^E \times LW$$

With SC the Scaling coefficient, LW the live weight and E the exponent

According to GUM (2008), the combined uncertainty of the heat production is defined as follows:

$$u_c(\Phi_{Tot}) = \sqrt{\left(\frac{\partial \Phi_{Tot}}{\partial SC} \times u(SC) \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial \Phi_{Tot}}{\partial LW} \times u(LW) \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial \Phi_{Tot}}{\partial E} \times u(E) \right)^2}$$

Uncertainties have been calculated with both the GUM and GUM-S1 (i.e. Monte-Carlo) methods. Similar results have been found and are shown in the figures hereafter.

Uncertainties associated to the total heat production have been calculated for each day over an entire rearing period (100 days) corresponding to a variation in live weight between 30.68-122.69 kg

The different standard uncertainties for the input variables are listed in the table below:

Variable X	Notati on	Value X	Standard uncertainty u(X)
Scaling coefficient	<i>SC</i>	15.97	1.05*
Exponent	<i>E</i>	-0.40	0.03*
Pig Live Weight (kg)	<i>LW</i>	30.68-122.69	1 %**

*From Ramirez et al., 2022

** The pig live weight uncertainty of 1 % corresponds to a series of weighing taking into account 72 pigs.

The partial derivatives are calculated as:

$$\frac{\partial \Phi_{Tot}}{\partial SC} = LW^{E+1} \quad ; \quad \frac{\partial \Phi_{Tot}}{\partial LW} = SC \times (E + 1) \times LW^E \quad ; \quad \frac{\partial \Phi_{Tot}}{\partial E} = SC \times LW^{E+1} \times \ln(LW)$$

Ultimately, the evolution of heat production with uncertainties for each time step is shown in the figure hereafter (red and blue color for GUM and GUM-S1 methods respectively).

We estimated that the relative uncertainty for Φ_{Tot} was equal at 29 % with this data set and the assumptions chosen for the uncertainties associated with the model input data.

In the table below, we can see that the main source of uncertainty arises from the estimation of the exponent and this could be probably reduced in the future with new experiments to develop new models that could better take into account genetics, the impact of temperature and type of feed.

Uncertainty Budgets (%)		
Body Weight	$\left(\frac{\partial \Phi_{Tot}}{\partial LW} \times u(LW)\right)^2 / u_c(\Phi_{Tot})^2$	0.2
Scaling Factor	$\left(\frac{\partial \Phi_{Tot}}{\partial SC} \times u(SC)\right)^2 / u_c(\Phi_{Tot})^2$	21.1
Exponent	$\left(\frac{\partial \Phi_{Tot}}{\partial E} \times u(E)\right)^2 / u_c(\Phi_{Tot})^2$	78.7

b - Total animal CO₂ production in the barn

According to GUM, the combined uncertainty is defined as follow

$$\begin{aligned}
 u_c(Q_{CO_2}) &= \sqrt{\left(\frac{\partial Q_{CO_2}}{\partial \Phi_{Tot}} \times u_c(\Phi_{Tot})\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial Q_{CO_2}}{\partial CO_{2_hpu}} \times u(CO_{2_hpu})\right)^2} \\
 &= \sqrt{(CO_{2_hpu} \times u_c(\Phi_{Tot}))^2 + (u(CO_{2_hpu}) \times \Phi_{Tot})^2}
 \end{aligned}$$

Variable X	Notati on	Value X	Standard uncertainty u(X)
Total heat production of the animal (W)	Φ_{Tot}	125-286	15-45

Animal number	Nb_{Animal}	72	0
Heat Producing Unit for CO ₂ (L animal ⁻¹) W ⁻¹	$CO_{2_{hpu}}$	0.185	0.015*

*This value has been chosen regarding the review made by Pedersen et al. (2008)

In the same way, the figure below describes the evolution of animal CO₂ production in the barn for each day over an entire rearing period.

We estimated that the relative uncertainty for Q_{CO_2} was equal at 33 % with this data set and the assumptions chosen for the uncertainties associated with the model input data.

7.2 Concerning the uncertainty budgets, we can see the following:

Uncertainty Budgets (%)		
Heat production	$\left(\frac{\partial Q_{CO_2}}{\partial \Phi_{Tot}} \times u_c(\Phi_{Tot}) \right)^2 / u_c(Q_{CO_2})^2$	76
Animal CO ₂ production per HPU	$\left(\frac{\partial Q_{CO_2}}{\partial CO_{2_{hpu}}} \times u(CO_{2_{hpu}}) \right)^2 / u_c(Q_{CO_2})^2$	24

7.3 Dairy cows heat

a - Dairy cows total heat production

To assess the total heat production of dairy cow we rely on the following equation given by CIGR (2002):

$$\varphi_{tot} = 5.6 \times LW^{0.75} + 22 \times FCM + 1.6 \cdot 10^{-5} \times P^3$$

$$FCM = 0.4 \times M + 15 \times F \times M$$

with LW the live weight, FCM the fat corrected milk, P the pregnancy duration.

The different standard uncertainties for the input variables are listed in the table below:

Variable X	Notation	Value X	Standard uncertainty u(X)
Cow live weight (kg)	<i>LW</i>	650	150
Milk (kg.day ⁻¹ .cow ⁻¹)	<i>M</i>	20	10
Fat (kg.fat/kg.milk)	<i>F</i>	0.040	0.005
Pregnancy duration (day)	<i>P</i>	150	150

Uncertainties calculated with GUM-S1 method only (GUM method not adapted for non-linear equations).

We estimated that the relative uncertainty for φ_{Tot} was equal at 41 % with this data set and the assumptions chosen for the uncertainties associated with the model input data. This could be reduced in cases where very precise information is available on each cow in the herd, which was not the case with the data set used. We were in a rather unfavourable situation for obtaining reduced uncertainty.

The main source of uncertainty arises from the estimation of the Fat Correct milk.

Uncertainty Ratios (%)	
Body Weight	17.3
Fat Corrected Milk	53.7
Pregnancy	29.1

b - Animal CO₂ production per cow

According to GUM-S1, the combined uncertainty is defined as follow:

Variable X	Notation	Value X	Standard uncertainty u(X)
Total heat production of the animal (W)	Φ_{Tot}	1250	260
Heat Producing Unit for CO ₂ (L animal ⁻¹) W ⁻¹	CO_{2hpu}	0.185	0.015*

*This value has been chosen regarding the review made by Pedersen et al. (2008)

The following figure presents the probability density of the CO₂ emission corresponding to a mean value of 230 liters of CO₂ (+/- 100 L with k=2).

We estimated that the relative uncertainty for Q_{CO_2} was equal at 44 % with this data set and the assumptions chosen for the uncertainties associated with the model input data.

7.4 Broiler heat production

a - Broiler total heat production

To assess the total heat production, we rely on the following equation given by CIGR (2002):

$$\Phi_{Tot} = SC \times LW^E \times LW$$

With SC the scaling coefficient, LW the live weight and E the exponent.

The combined uncertainty of the heat production is defined as follows:

$$u_c(\Phi_{Tot}) = \sqrt{\left(\frac{\partial\Phi_{Tot}}{\partial SC} \times u(SC)\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial\Phi_{Tot}}{\partial LW} \times u(LW)\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial\Phi_{Tot}}{\partial E} \times u(E)\right)^2}$$

Uncertainties have been calculated with both the GUM and GUM-S1 (i.e. Monte-Carlo) methods. Similar results have been found and shown in the figures below.

Uncertainties associated to the total heat production have been calculated for each day over an entire rearing period (32) corresponding to a variation in live weight between 0.040-1.71kg.

The different standard uncertainties are listed in the table below:

Variable X	Notation	Value X	Standard uncertainty u(X)
Scaling coefficient	<i>SC</i>	10.62	1.05*
Exponent	<i>E</i>	-0.25	0.03*
Broiler Live Weight (kg)	<i>LW</i>	0.040-1.71	0.5 %×LW**

*We kept the same values used for pigs (Ramirez et al., 2022)

**The broiler live weight uncertainty of 0.5 % corresponds to a series of weighing taking into account 100 animals each.

The partial derivatives are calculated as:

$$\frac{\partial \Phi_{Tot}}{\partial SC} = LW^{E+1} \quad ; \quad \frac{\partial \Phi_{Tot}}{\partial LW} = SC \times (E + 1) \times LW^E \quad ; \quad \frac{\partial \Phi_{Tot}}{\partial E} = SC \times LW^{E+1} \times \ln(LW)$$

Ultimately, the evolution of heat production with uncertainties for each time step is shown in the figure hereafter (red and blue color for GUM and GUM-S1 methods respectively).

We estimated that the relative uncertainty for Φ_{Tot} was equal at 20 % with this data set and the assumptions chosen for the uncertainties associated with the model input data.

The main source of uncertainty arises from the estimation of the scaling factor, which could be decreased by adapting the coefficient and its corresponding uncertainty to the specific measurement conditions. It has to be noted that the uncertainty of the scaling coefficient is taken from the pig fattening one, therefore it could overestimate the uncertainty in this case. This could be probably reduced in the future with new experiments to develop new models that could better take into account genetics, the impact of temperature and type of feed.

Uncertainty Budgets (%)		
Body Weight	$\left(\frac{\partial \Phi_{Tot}}{\partial LW} \times u(LW)\right)^2 / u_c(\Phi_{Tot})^2$	0.1
Scaling Factor	$\left(\frac{\partial \Phi_{Tot}}{\partial SC} \times u(SC)\right)^2 / u_c(\Phi_{Tot})^2$	88.4
Exponent	$\left(\frac{\partial \Phi_{Tot}}{\partial E} \times u(E)\right)^2 / u_c(\Phi_{Tot})^2$	11.5

b - Total animal CO₂ production in the barn

According to GUM, the combined uncertainty is defined as follow:

$$u_c(Q_{CO_2}) = \sqrt{(CO_{2_hpu} \times u_c(\Phi_{Tot}))^2 + (u(CO_{2_hpu}) \times \Phi_{Tot})^2}$$

Variable X	Notation	Value X	Standard uncertainty u(X)
Total heat production of the animal	Φ_{Tot}	4170-69200	570-6950
Animal number	Nb_{Animal}	4364-4580	0
Heat Producing Unit for CO ₂	CO_{2_hpu}	0.185	0.015*

*This value has been chosen regarding the review made by Pedersen et al. (2008)

In the same way, the figure below describes the evolution of animal CO₂ production in the barn for each day over an entire rearing period.

We estimated that the relative uncertainty for Q_{CO_2} was equal at 26 % with this data set and the assumptions chosen for the uncertainties associated with the model input data.

Uncertainty Budgets (%)		
Heat production	$\left(\frac{\partial Q_{CO_2}}{\partial \Phi_{Tot}} \times u_c(\Phi_{Tot})\right)^2 / u_c(Q_{CO_2})^2$	37
Animal production per HPU CO ₂	$\left(\frac{\partial Q_{CO_2}}{\partial CO_{2_hpu}} \times u(CO_{2_hpu})\right)^2 / u_c(Q_{CO_2})^2$	63

7.5 References

Pedersen, S. & Sällvik, K., 2002. 4th Report of Working Group on Climatization of Animal Houses Heat and moisture production at animal and house levels. Research Centre Bygholm, Danish Institute of Agricultural Sciences.

GUM, 2008. Evaluation of measurement data – Guide to the expression of Uncertainty in Measurement (GUM), 1st edition.

Pedersen, S., Blanes-Vidal, V., Jørgensen, H., Chwalibog, A., Haeussermann, A., Heetkamp, M.J.W. & Aarnink, A.J.A. (2008). Carbon dioxide production in animal houses: A literature review. *Agricultural Engineering International: CIGR Journal*.

Ramirez, B.C., Hoff, S.J., Hayes, M.D., Brown-Brandl, T., Harmon, J. D. & Rohrer, G.A., 2022. A review of swine heat production: 2003 to 2020. *Frontiers in Animal Science*, 3, 908434.

8 Annex 2 - Uncertainty assessment on Carbon and Nitrogen mass balance deficits for different animal productions

(INRAE, LNE) (Connected to 3.2 CO₂ Balance method)

This Annex contains calculations of uncertainties of mass balance deficits for different animal production systems. The calculations are performed as examples based on data sets from past experiments conducted in commercial animal houses or at experimental stations. We have assessed the uncertainties in the input variables either on the basis of existing information or expert opinion. The results obtained provide an idea of the orders of magnitude of the uncertainty associated to the mass balance deficit and to the input variables of the model.

The “generic model” is:

$$X_{Deficit} = X_{Input} - X_{Output}$$

$$u(X_{Deficit}) = \sqrt{u(X_{Input})^2 + u(X_{Output})^2}$$

X is for C(Carbon) or N (Nitrogen)

For each animal production, it has been adapted to its specificities in the calculations presented below.

8.1 Fattening pigs (experimental pig house, Brittany agricultural chamber dataset)

Calculations have been made for 2 batches.

a - Carbon mass balance

For the 2 batches, the Carbon deficit was estimated to be around 4700 kg, namely 66 % of the total carbon input and with an uncertainty of 11 %.

In the table below, we indicated all the input variables for the models and the associated uncertainties.

Variable	Notation	X ₁ (batch 1)	u(X ₁)	X ₂ (batch 2)	u(X ₂)
C _{Input}					
Initial pig mass (kg)	<i>LW_{Pigs,i}</i>	2209	22	2201.5	22
Carbon ratio in pigs	<i>CR_{Pigs}</i>	0.177	0.018	0.177	0.018
Growth feeding mass (kg)	<i>m_{GF}</i>	6655	133	6640	133
Dry matter (DM) in growth feeding	<i>DM_{GF}</i>	0.883	0.008	0.876	0.008

Finish feeding mass (kg)	m_{FF}	10150	203	9963	199
Dry matter (DM) in finish feeding	DM_{FF}	0.888	0.008	0.881	0.008
Carbon in feeding dry matter	$CR_{Feeding}$	0.45	0.045	0.45	0.045
C_{Output}					
Final pigs mass (kg)	$LW_{Pigs.f}$	8834	88	8877	89
Slurry volume (L)	V_{Slurry}	25231	2523	26200	2620
Carbon ratio in slurry	CR_{Slurry}	0.034	0.0034	0.024	0.0024

8.2 Figure 1: Carbon mass balance for batch 1.

8.3 Figure 2: Carbon mass balance for batch 2.

Uncertainty budget (%)	Batch 1	Batch 2
C_{Input}		
Initial live weight	4.2	4.3
Feeding	95.8	95.7
C_{Output}		
Final live weight	50.9	53.9
Slurry	49.1	46.1

b - Nitrogen mass balance

For this experiment, the N deficit for both batches was estimated to be around 65 kg, namely 16 % of the total nitrogen input and with an uncertainty of 47 %.

In the table below, we indicated all the input variables for the models and the associated uncertainties.

Variable	Notation	X_1	$u(X_1)$	X_2	$u(X_2)$
N_{Input}					
Initial total pig mass (kg)	$LW_{Pigs,i}$	2209	22	2201.5	22
Lean Meat percentage	LMP	61.5	2	61.5	2
Nitrogen ratio in crude protein	NR_{CP}	0.16	0.01	0.16	0.01
Growth feeding mass (kg)	m_{GF}	6655	200	6640	199
CP in growth feeding	CP_{GF}	0.140	0.007	0.137	0.007
Finish feeding mass (kg)	m_{FF}	10150	305	9963	299
CP in finish feeding	CP_{FF}	0.123	0.006	0.125	0.006
N_{Output}					
Final pigs mass (kg)	$LW_{Pigs,f}$	8834	88	8877	89
Slurry volume (L)	V_{Slurry}	25231	2523	26200	2620
Nitrogen ratio in slurry	NR_{Slurry}	4.35	0.87	3.15	0.3

8.4 Figure 3: Nitrogen mass balance for batch 1.

Figure 4: Nitrogen mass balance for batch 2.

Uncertainty Ratios (%)	Batch 1	Batch 2
Input		
Initial live weight	14.1	14.1
Feeding	85.9	85.9
Output		
Final live weight	52.6	53.6
Slurry	29.7	30.3

8.5 Turkeys (commercial poultry house, INRAE dataset)

a - Carbon mass balance

For this experiment, the Carbon deficit was estimated to be about 44750 kg, namely 59 % of the total carbon input and with an uncertainty of 8 %.

In the table below, we indicated all the input variables for the models and the associated uncertainties.

Variable	Notation	X_1	$u(X_1)$
C_{Input}			
Mean male number	Nb_{Male}	3746	4
Mean female number	Nb_{Female}	3873	4
Initial male turkey mass (kg)	LW_{Male_i}	0.050	0.001
Initial female turkey mass (kg)	LW_{Female_i}	0.050	0.001
Dry matter (DM) in poultry	DM_{Animal}	0.40	0.06
Carbon ratio in DM poultry	CR_{DM_Animal}	0.50	0.05
Total feeding mass (kg)	$m_{Feeding}$	162764	4883
Dry matter (DM) in feeding	$DM_{Feeding}$	0.88	0.01
Carbon ratio in DM feeding	$CR_{DM_Feeding}$	0.50	0.05
Total bedding mass (kg)	$m_{Bedding}$	10740	322
Dry matter (DM) in bedding	$DM_{Feeding}$	0.85	0.01
Carbon ratio in bedding	$CR_{Bedding}$	0.50	0.05
C_{Output}			
Final male turkey mass (kg)	LW_{Male_f}	14.20	0.28

Final female turkey mass (kg)	LW_{Female_f}	5.00	0.10
Manure mass (kg)	m_{Manure}	79890	2397
Carbon ratio in manure	CR_{Manure}	0.02135	0.002

8.6 Figure 5: Carbon mass balance.

Uncertainty Ratios (%)	
Input	
Initial live weight	0.5
Feeding	85.5
Bedding	14.0
Output	
Metabolized	46.1
Manure	53.9

b - Nitrogen mass balance

For this experiment, the nitrogen deficit was estimated to be about 1070 kg, namely 19 % of the total nitrogen input and with an uncertainty of 25 %.

In the table below, we indicated all the input variables for the models and the associated uncertainties.

Variable	Notation	X_1	$u(X_1)$
N_{Input}			
Mean male number	Nb_{Male}	3746	4
Mean female number	Nb_{Female}	3873	4
Initial male turkey mass (kg)	LW_{Male_i}	0.050	0.001
Initial female turkey mass (kg)	LW_{Female_i}	0.050	0.001
Crude protein (CP)	CP_{Animal}	0.21	0.01

Nitrogen ratio in CP	NR_{CP}	0.16	0.01
Total feeding mass (kg)	$m_{Feeding}$	162764	4883
Nitrogen ratio in feeding	$NR_{Feeding}$	$3.14-4.24 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$1.57-2.12 \cdot 10^{-3}$
Total bedding mass (kg)	$m_{Bedding}$	10740	322
Nitrogen ratio in bedding	$NR_{Bedding}$	$4.84 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$4.84 \cdot 10^{-4}$
N_{Output}			
Final male turkey mass (kg)	LW_{Male_f}	14.20	0.28
Final female turkey mass (kg)	LW_{Female_f}	5.00	0.10
Manure mass (kg)	m_{Manure}	79890	2397
Nitrogen ratio in manure	NR_{Manure}	0.025	0.0025

8.7 Figure 6: Nitrogen mass balance.

Uncertainty Ratios (%)	
Input	
Initial live weight	0.5
Feeding	96.0
Bedding	3.5
Output	
Metabolized	42.4
Manure	57.6

8.8 Broilers (experimental poultry house, INRAE/ITAVI dataset)

a - Carbon mass balance

For this experiment, the Carbon deficit was estimated to be about 1000 kg, namely 14 % of the total carbon input and with an uncertainty of 10 %.

In the table below, we indicated all the input variables for the models and the associated uncertainties.

Variable	Notation	X_1	$u(X_1)$	X_2	$u(X_2)$
C_{Input}					
Initial animal number	Nb_{Animal_i}	4580	0	4580	0
Initial poultry mass (kg)	$LW_{Poultry_i}$	0.040	$2 \cdot 10^{-4}$	0.040	$2 \cdot 10^{-4}$
Dry matter (DM) in poultry	$DM_{Poultry}$	0.30	0.06	0.30	0.06
Carbon ratio in DM poultry	$CR_{DM_Poultry}$	0.50	0.05	0.50	0.05
Consumption index	$CI_{Feeding}$	1.29-1.98	$1.3 \cdot 2 \cdot 10^{-3}$	1.29-1.98	$1.3 \cdot 2 \cdot 10^{-3}$
Daily weight gain	ADI	$0.44 \cdot 2.7 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$0.44 \cdot 2.7 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$0.44 \cdot 2.7 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$0.44 \cdot 2.7 \cdot 10^{-6}$
Dry matter in feeding	$DM_{Feeding}$	0.85	0.02	0.85	0.02
Carbon ratio in DM feeding	$CR_{DM_Feeding}$	0.50	0.05	0.50	0.05
Bedding mass (kg)	$m_{Bedding}$	320	3.2	320	3.2
Dry matter in bedding	$DM_{Bedding}$	0.85	0.02	0.85	0.02
Carbon ratio in DM bedding	$CR_{DM_Bedding}$	300	10	300	10
C_{Output}					
Final animal number	Nb_{Animal}	4364-4580	0	4312-4580	0
Poultry mass (kg)	$LW_{Poultry}$	0.040-1.71	$8.6 \cdot 10^{-3}$	0.040-1.69	$8.5 \cdot 10^{-3}$
Death animal number	Nb_{Death}	0-216	0	0-268	0
Carbon ratio excreted in bedding	CR_{E-B}	0.24	0.02	0.24	0.02

8.9 Figure 7: Carbon mass balance for batch 1.

8.10 Figure 8: Carbon mass balance for batch 2.

Uncertainty Ratios (%)	Source	Batch 1	Batch 2	Source	Batch 1	Batch 2	
	Input				Output		
	Initial live weight	0.9	0.9		Metabolized	39.4	39.0
	Feeding	96.3	96.3		Manure	60.0	60.4
	Bedding	2.8	2.8		Mortality	0.6	0.6

b - Nitrogen mass balance

For this experiment, the Nitrogen deficit was estimated to be about 20 kg, namely 6 % of the total nitrogen input and with an uncertainty of 68 %.

In the table below, we indicated all the input variables for the models and the associated uncertainties.

Variable	Notation	X ₁	u(X ₁)	X ₂	u(X ₂)
N_{Input}					
Initial animal number	<i>Nb_{Animal_i}</i>	4580	0	4580	0
Initial poultry mass (kg)	<i>LW_{Poultry_i}</i>	0.040	2.10 ⁻⁴	0.040	2.10 ⁻⁴
Nitrogen ratio in poultry	<i>NR_{Poultry}</i>	0.029	2.10 ⁻³	0.029	2.10 ⁻³
Consumption index	<i>CI_{Feeding}</i>	1.29-1.98	1.3-2.10 ⁻³	1.29-1.98	1.3-2.10 ⁻³
Average daily income	<i>ADI</i>	0.44-2.7.10 ⁻³	0.44-2.7.10 ⁻⁶	0.44-2.7.10 ⁻³	0.44-2.7.10 ⁻⁶
Nitrogen ratio in feeding	<i>NR_{Feeding}</i>	0.0298	2.10 ⁻³	0.0298	2.10 ⁻³
Bedding mass (kg)	<i>m_{Bedding}</i>	320	3.2	320	3.2
Dry matter in bedding	<i>DM_{Bedding}</i>	0.85	0.02	0.85	0.02
Carbon ratio in dry matter bedding	<i>C_{Bedding}</i>	0.50	0.05	0.50	0.05
Carbon/Nitrogen ratio in bedding	<i>CNR_{Bedding}</i>	300	10	300	10
N_{Output}					
Animal number	<i>Nb_{Animal}</i>	4364-4580	0	4312-4580	0
Poultry mass (kg)	<i>LW_{Poultry}</i>	0.040-1.71	8.6.10 ⁻³	0.040-1.69	8.5.10 ⁻³
Death animal number	<i>Nb_{Death}</i>	0-216	0	0-268	0
Volatilized nitrogen ratio	<i>NR_{Vol}</i>	0.32	0.08	0.32	0.08
NH ₃ emission (kg)	<i>N_{NH3}</i>	22.14	4.51	18.68	3.81
N ₂ O emission (kg)	<i>N_{N2O}</i>	3.7.10 ⁻²	0	2.3.10 ⁻²	0

Figure 9: Nitrogen mass balance for batch 1.

Figure 10: Nitrogen mass balance for batch 2.

Uncertainty Ratios (%)	Source	Batch 1	Batch 2	Source	Batch 1	Batch 2
	Input			Output		
Initial weight live		0.4	0.4	Metabolized	22.1	21.2
Feeding		99.5	99.5	Manure	77.6	78.5
Bedding		0.1	0.1	Death	0.3	0.3

9 Annex 3 – example of output of the simplified method (see 3.6) when comparing one farm to a population of farms by using the “signature” concept

The implementation of the simplified method during the CCCFarming project over 60 farms, with 4 measurements (“4 seasons”) in each farm, showed both the variability between farms and the variability between days of measurement. We proposed the concept of “signature” to analyse this diversity without aggregating all observations in only one unique figure. It can help identifying directions of progress on farm scale from showing risks of high emissions in one farm when compared to a similar farm in the same territory (Vergé & Robin, 2024). The “signature” is a histogram of frequency of the observed emission in 5 classes centered on the value of the national emission factor. The categories of “signatures” were not explained with farm observations such as feed level, milk production, house type or manure management (Robin et al., 2024). Nevertheless, the method showed its ability to identify “good practices” (low emission houses) and “hot-spots” (farms with a risk of high emission that would need further investigations).

The figure below shows the results of both barns monitored in Agroscope’s experimental dairy housing during A1.5.2. The method shows similar results for both compartments (“barns”). The simplified method is not accurate enough to detect the small differences revealed with the dual tracer-ratio method. However, it can help to detect farms where emissions are either repeatedly higher than the average, or repeatedly lower, therefore helping farm advisors to encourage good practices and institutions to improve the trueness of their emission factors from enhanced coverage of the diversity of emissions within current livestock farming systems.

References

- Vergé, X., & Robin, P., 2024. How to estimate GHG and NH₃ emission factors in open livestock buildings? improvements of the « simplified method ». EmiLi 2024 Conference. 5 International Symposium on Gas and Dust Emissions from Livestock Valencia (Spain), 24-26 September 2024. Poster. <https://emiliconference.com/>
- Robin, P., Vergé, X., Becciolini, V., Cieślak, A., Edouard, N., Fehmer, L., Galama, P., Hargreaves, P., Juškienė, V., Kadžiene, G., Schilder, H., Leso, L., Lissy, A.-S., Priekulis, J., Rees, B., Ruska, D. & Szumacher-Strabel, M., 2024. Measuring ammonia and greenhouse gas emissions of dairy cattle house in 60 farms over eight countries. EmiLi 2024 Conference. 5 International Symposium on Gas and Dust Emissions from Livestock Valencia (Spain), 24-26 September 2024. Poster. <https://emiliconference.com/>

quantiAGREMI Project - Field monitoring and assessment - farmer management tool - version 2

p.2

quantiAGREMI Project - Field monitoring and assessment - farmer management tool - version 2

p.2

Results of all emission measurements obtained with the simplified method in both compartments/barns of the Agroscope farm in Tänikon

Please delete before you submit your report
Document Control Page

Title:	Document	European Partnership on Metrology Contracts		
		Reporting Template 7: Deliverable Cover Sheet		
Code:	Document	P-CON-TMP-207	Version 1.1	
Control:	Document	Approved: Programme Manager	2024-11-25	

HISTORY OF CHANGES			
VERSION	DATE	PUBLICATION	CHANGE
<u>1.0</u>		2023-08-24	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Initial version.
<u>1.1</u>		2024-11-25	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> History of changes added. Public confidentiality status option updated.